

INTEGRATION OF HETEROGENEOUS DATA & EVIDENCE TOWARDS REGULATORY & HTA ACCEPTANCE

WP6 Policy recommendations
to enable Regulatory and
HTA decision making

About this report

This report was written in 2025 as Deliverable 6.4 in the IDERHA project, and submitted to IHI on 30th May 2025¹.

The IDERHA project aims to build an open, disease agnostic, federated data space which enables connectivity, access, use and reuse of digital health data, and develop consensus policy recommendations on health data access and heterogeneous health research (e.g. RWE) for regulatory and HTA decision-making.

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Executive summary

IDERHA D6.4

IDERHA is developing a health data integration and analytics platform that combines heterogeneous health data sources, including EHRs, medical images, and patient collected data. This ambition will be realised in a relatively complex policy and legislative context and is now being accelerated and harmonised across Europe via the European Health Data Space (EHDS) Regulation.

Within IDERHA's WP6, Task 6.2 has been scanning this European and international landscape of policy and legislative instruments to highlight those that have a bearing on how the IDERHA seeks to acquire, collect, process and use health data, including its intended development and use of AI and mobile applications to be used by patients. The Task has signposted relevant instruments, or parts of instruments, to which various IDERHA work packages will need to conform and draw particular attention to policy and legislative gaps requiring the attention of external stakeholders and policymakers. Task 6.2 findings have been presented at meetings of the Integrated Data Access Governance Council (IDAGC), which is comprised of IDERHA stakeholders and external thought leaders.

This deliverable, D6.4, updates and extends an earlier deliverable, D6.1, and is the final deliverable from Task 6.2. It presents (in Appendix 2) the main areas of potential policy and strategy (including European Regulations) that can influence the IDERHA secondary data reuse landscape. The most important areas have been elaborated on by invited project experts to explain the policy instrument(s), how each might impact IDERHA, and how IDERHA should respond. These templates are included in Appendix 1.

Some issues proved to be cross cutting across multiple policy instruments and templates, and they have been synthesised and discussed in this document.

KEY ISSUE 1:

The legal basis of consent and how large-scale health data research can be undertaken in compliance with the GDPR. GDPR-compliant informed consent is difficult to use as the legal basis for processing when establishing a data platform that might, in the future, support many uses of the data. It is especially challenging to obtain consent to use as the legal basis when so many data sets come from healthcare, in which consent for healthcare use is implied rather than explicitly captured, and there is no formalised consent for secondary use purposes. Other legal bases, therefore, need to be considered.

KEY ISSUE 2:

The incentives and disincentives to data sharing from two perspectives: the data holder and the patients. The data holder is a functional role that, in practice, could be any of a wide range of organisational types or may be a decision-making actor within the organisation, such as the principal investigator or a data protection officer. The major tension seems to focus on the potential for a data user to derive and exploit insights that the data holder would have preferred themselves to make and use, if this capacity, capability, foresight or willingness existed within their own organisation. This can manifest as commercial competitiveness or academic reputation and publication competitiveness.

KEY ISSUE 3:

The opportunities for IDERHA presented by the forthcoming European Health Data Space. This Regulation, to some extent, takes away this issue of incentives and disincentives by mandating data holders to make data sets shareable through Health Data Access Bodies. It also introduces some challenges for data holders, especially for proprietary data sets that are (mainly from the industry side) connected with intellectual property or trade secrets or (mainly from the public side) constrained by terms of references to specific purposes or organisational type or which require scientific assessment before the intended analysis plan is approved.

KEY ISSUE 4:

The obligations of IDERHA to comply with the EU AI Act are discussed, in particular, the need to consider how it will demonstrate the quality and representativeness (lack of or minimal bias) of its training, testing and evaluating data for AI development.

KEY ISSUE 5:

Gaining and maintaining citizen trust in the reuse of their data will be critical since the EHDS Regulation will introduce the right for any European citizen to opt out of the secondary use of data. This topic of trust has been examined in detail through focus groups which highlighted the importance to individuals of being informed quickly and honestly by the data holder of any data breach that has occurred in the organisation relating to research data, whether or not that individual was included in the breach. However, trust must also be built through proactive strategies that account for future political, cultural, and social uncertainties, particularly those affecting vulnerable groups. Static codes of conduct and narrow compliance models may prove to be insufficient. Instead, trust governance must include adaptive, anticipatory frameworks that evolve with emerging risks to ensure continuous public trust. This includes incorporating mechanisms for continual engagement with patient or patient representatives from the beginning stages of system design and governance.

Task 6.2 is part of work package 6 that contains other tasks, activities and deliverables that will extend the work reported here, to which task 6.2 experts will contribute. The recommendations arising from this work will be taken up within Task 6.3 and included in its future deliverables.

Table of content

1.	Introduction	7
1.1	Overview of the deliverable	8
2.	Methodology	9
2.1	Objective and scope	9
2.2	Development of the topic map	9
2.3	Development of the policy briefing template	10
2.4	Focus group interviews	12
3.	Extraction of key themes	13
3.1	Consent	13
3.2	European health data space	15
3.3	Complying with the EU AI Act	17
4.	Incentives and disincentives to data sharing	20
4.1	Data holder incentives and disincentives to share data	20
4.2	Retaining the trust of the patients within a data set	21
4.3	Exploring trust-building measures through the lens of breakdown	22
5.	Anticipating trust breakdowns	24
5.1	Synthesis of focus group interviews	24
5.2	Minor data breaches and social mistrust as a barrier	25
5.3	Organising a standard balanced - Balancing particularity and standardisation in mitigation strategies	26
5.4	Uncertainties in trust-building efforts	27
5.6	Concluding analysis	28
6.	Conclusion	29
7.	Bibliography	31
8.	Appendix I: Policy brief templates	34
8.1	GDPR: Stakeholder awareness and competencies for legal and ethical data sharing and reuse	35
8.2	GDPR: Current potential gaps in cross country pseudonymisation of data	37
8.3	GDPR: Anonymization and new technological challenges	39
8.4	AI: Compliance with the AI ethics principles	40
8.5	AI: Regulatory gaps in the AI Act under revision	41
8.6	Interoperability: Recommendation on a European Electronic Health Record exchange format	42
8.7	Data Provenance and Lineage (traceability)	44
8.8	Data Types & Formats	47
8.9	Consent (i) voluntary	49
8.10	Consent (ii) specific	50
8.11	Consent (iii) informed	51
8.12	Consent (iv) broad	52
8.13	Consent (v) explicit for special categories of data	53
8.14	Other legal bases	54
8.15	Health data quality and utility for the secondary use of health data in the European Union - Implications for IDERHA from the European Health Data Space (EHDS) Regulation proposal	55

8.16	Protection of data privacy and security within the European Health Data Space (EHDS) using Secure Processing Environments (SPEs) for data access and analysis	56
8.17	EHDS interoperability with external infrastructures	58
8.18	Uncertainty of the access procedure for the developers and tool installation (WiP)	59
8.19	Common Data Models	60
8.20	Protection of Confidential Commercial Information (CCI) & trade secrets	62
8.21	Evolving legal landscape (mainly EHDS)	63
8.22	Anonymization	64
8.23	Regulatory impact of requirements for high-risk AI systems under the EU AI Act	65
8.24	Requirements related to data and data governance under the EU AI Act	66
8.25	Dynamic consent	67
8.26	Delays in Data Sharing	69
8.27	Challenges of diversity and internationalisation in data sharing in health	70
9.	Appendix 2: Topic map	72
9.1	Strategic investment objective	73
9.2	Interoperability standards	74
9.3	Data quality	74
9.4	Artificial intelligence	75
9.5	Data sharing and data access	75
9.6	Data protection	76
9.7	Data infrastructures	76
9.8	Digital health tools and DTx	77
9.9	Other initiatives	77

1. Introduction

IDERHA is developing a health data integration and analytics platform that combines heterogeneous health data sources, including EHRs, medical images, and patient collected data, to advance the development and delivery of personalised medicine, exemplified in lung cancer. It will utilise AI to develop risk stratification and prediction models that can assist in the personalisation of treatment, early detection of deterioration, and recommend appropriate care pathway adaptations. Its data and analytics will deliver value across a spectrum from near patient to scientific research, including the future development of innovations in medical technology and medicines. IDERHA has selected to exemplify and demonstrate this platform in the domain of lung cancer but aims to develop generic components, disease agnostic and capable of application to other cancers and other short- and long-term conditions as part of its overall scope of operation.

IDERHA will need to integrate large volumes of sensitive (GDPR special category) personal health data, perform machine learning and develop AI solutions that will be used by patients, researchers and clinicians. To deliver value for individual patients, some of its data flows and processing will need to retain patient identification, including collecting patient preferences and dynamic consent regarding the secondary use of their data. Others will need to use pseudonymised data to manage longitudinal linkage and multi-source linkage correctly, and other uses can be anonymised. IDERHA will enable the reuse of health data across borders, at a European scale, and reuse by industry as well as academic and health systems organisations. Its development and use of AI must be ethical, equitable, risk-managed, safe and transparent.

IDERHA's ambition will be realised in a relatively complex policy and legislative context that is now being accelerated and harmonised across Europe via the European Health Data Space (EHDS) Regulation and additionally impacted by the EU AI Act. At the same time, the application of the GDPR for the reuse of health data is becoming more stringent due to public and decision-maker concerns about how health data could be used detrimentally, inappropriately exploited, and might lead to the development of AI that harms individuals and groups (Marcus et al. 2022). There are also calls for, and potential policy movement in the direction of greater transparency to the public, accountability to the public and greater control over the processing of personal data by individuals (TEHDAS 2023a). This transparency is also a requirement for the secondary use of health data via the EHDS.

The objective of IDERHA Work Package 6 is to develop recommendations to accelerate Real World Evidence (RWE) policy development to meet the current and future advances in the digitization of health data, research methods, and health care innovations. Task 6.2 of WP6 has been set up to scan the European and international landscape of policy and legislative instruments to highlight those that have a bearing on the ways in which the IDERHA seeks to acquire, collect, process and use health data, including its intended development and use of AI and mobile applications to be used by patients. The task has examined this policy and legislative landscape from the perspective of the impact that it has on the future acceptability, sustainability, and scalability of IDERHA's solutions. The task has signposted relevant instruments, or parts of instruments, to which various IDERHA (and other similar projects) need to conform to help foster the conditions of success for IDERHA and others to thrive within Europe. This task complements WP5, which focuses more explicitly on the methodological approaches that the project work plan needs to take to comply with Regulations and legislation as it is now. The challenges it has identified have provided an essential input to Task 6.2. Task 6.2 has highlighted whether these instruments represent expected and good practices that the project should embrace or constraints that are not well suited to the mission of the project, but which we need to find appropriate ways of achieving compliance with, without prejudicing the success of the project. Instruments in this context are not limited to legislative instruments but include selected policies and strategies, international standards, guidelines and reports from authoritative bodies and academic publications.

The primary objective of Task 6.2 is to identify the policy and legislative gaps, thereby indicating areas requiring the attention of external stakeholders and policymakers. The IDERHA Integrated Data Access Governance Council [1] (IDAGC) was established to provide guidance to the project team and includes internal IDERHA representatives and external experts. Task 6.2 findings have been presented at meetings of the Integrated Data Access Governance Council (IDAGC). As the project progresses, their guidance will be sought on how best to influence change in the policy and legislative landscape and how to better favour an environment that enables large-scale learning from health data and the translation of that learning into improvements in care pathways and clinical guidelines.

1.1 Overview of the deliverable

This deliverable, D6.4, updates and extends the earlier deliverable, D6.1, and is the final deliverable from WP 6 Task 6.2. It presents (as a topic map in Appendix 2) the main areas of potential policy and strategy (including European Regulations) that can influence the secondary data reuse landscape on which IDERHA depends and could positively or negatively affect IDERHA's capabilities, acceptance, scalability or sustainability. The most important of these areas have been elaborated by various invited project experts to explain the policy instrument(s) of relevance, how each might impact IDERHA and how IDERHA should respond. These templates are all included in Appendix 1 (including those from the previous deliverable, for completeness).

Some issues proved to be cross cutting across multiple policy instruments and templates, which have been synthesised in this document, focusing on:

- the legal basis of consent and how large-scale health data research can be undertaken in compliance with the GDPR
- the opportunities for IDERHA presented by the forthcoming European Health Data Space, and also some challenges with acting as a data holder
- the obligations of IDERHA to comply with the EU AI Act,
- the incentives and disincentives to data sharing from two perspectives: the data holder and the data subject.

Given that the EHDS Regulation will introduce the right for any European citizen to opt out of the secondary use of data, gaining and maintaining citizen trust in the reuse of their data will be critical. Amongst the factors that might trigger a person to opt out or withdraw their implicit or explicit consent are scenarios that cause a loss of trust. To understand this issue better, focus groups were run with patients and separately with data holders and users to examine the impact of different situations that might jeopardise data subject trust and how this might be mitigated. The focus group findings are presented in this document.

The overarching mixed methods methodology for this work is first presented in the next chapter.

2. Methodology

Data for this deliverable is primarily collected using two methods. First, a template for producing concise, summarised executive briefings on key political and legislative instruments and their implications for the IDERHA project was created. Using this template, a portfolio of briefings was compiled within a conceptual, organisational structure that groups related instruments under key topic headings. An overarching topic map has been created to guide the collection of briefings by highlighting relevant task-related topic areas.

Second, to supplement the executive briefings and topic map, we conducted focus group interviews on trust and trust mitigation with patient representatives, representatives from marginalised groups, and data holders and owners. The interviews focused on how to establish trust, particularly how to mitigate trust in the event of data leakage or misuse, and the impact of related news stories. More details about the methods can be found below.

2.1 Objective and scope

The scope of Task 6.2 has been to identify and examine regulations, legislation, policy, guidelines and emerging practices relevant to the IDERHA work plan, as well as its wider adoption and sustainability. The overall task objective is to determine the implications for and potential impact on IDERHA and similar data sharing initiatives of these aspects.

2.2 Development of the topic map

To get an overview of relevant topics for the task to consider, a topic map was developed (See Appendix 2). The starting point for this topic map was to examine the project work plan, particularly the data acquisition, processing and sharing processes, that are intended and the results outputs to be generated. IDERHA is working with multiple data providers across Europe and is also engaging directly with patients to collect data through apps and wearables. Data can be accessed collectively through a federated health data platform that serves observational study and AI development purposes. Risk stratification and prediction models will later become embedded within digital tools that incorporate AI components for digital health trials at clinical sites. Other areas of the work plan examine and implement topics like AI ethics, explainability, and dynamic consent. A topic map was drawn up reflecting these areas of work as topics on which relevant policy and legislative instruments might have a bearing.

Subsequently, other EU-level instruments of significant importance were analysed to incorporate their main areas of focus into the topic map. These included the EU GDPR, the EHDS draft Regulation, the draft EU AI Act and the Data Governance Act. This enabled a second level of the topic map to be populated. These subtopics were used to map the main provisions of different instruments and served as topics on which to look for other instruments and/or good practices.

2.2.1 CHALLENGES AND STRATEGIES IDENTIFIED BY PREVIOUS EU PROJECTS

The next step was to consider the challenges and strategies adopted by current and recent key European health data projects. These included IMI EHR4CR (EHR4CR 2011), GetReal (GetReal Institute 2025), EMIF (EMIF 2017), EHDEN (EHDEN 2024), EU PEARL (EU PEARL 2023), Conception (ConcePTION 2019), H2O (H2O 2021), and Horizon 2020 projects, as well as support actions including ASSESS-CT (ASSESS-CT 2020), eStandards (eStandards 2017), DigitalHealthEurope (DigitalHealthEurope 2021b), European mHealthHub (European mHealthHub 2025), Label2Enable (Label2Enable 2025), and UNICOM (UNICOM 2024). Reports of well conducted multistakeholder consultations and engagements on health data related topics were also examined (DigitalHealthEurope 2020,2021a; I~HD and DHS 2021a, 2021b, 2022, 2023). The topic map was enriched to include areas in which policy, good practices, or other enabling solutions exist, some of which might be challenges that lack suitable policy coverage.

2.2.2 CONSULTATION WITH IDAGC

The resulting topic map was shared with partners in WP6 and then presented at the first IDAGC meeting. Feedback from these consultations was incorporated into the map. This revision process, aided by the IDAGC, constituted a central milestone and acted as a springboard for initial discussions of the council.

The topic map served as a conceptual model, and only some of the main branches and lower-level nodes have corresponding instruments. Higher-level topics in the topic map served as headers for the synthesis of many lower-level nodes and their IDERHA implications.

2.3 Development of the policy briefing template

As noted in the introduction, “instruments” for the purposes of this report are not limited to legislative documents but may include selected policies and strategies, international standards, guidelines and reports from authoritative bodies and academic publications.

Instruments identified through working with the topic map were summarised in individual policy brief templates. The completion of templates was facilitated by a set of standard headings with guiding notes. Links to the original material are included in the templates if they are openly accessible. The summary is intended to highlight the project relevant implications to data sharing initiatives and projects, identify current gaps in the policy landscape, and flag areas in need of further exploration. Complex instruments were split into several templates to keep the templates short, specific and easy to digest.

2.3.1 COLLECTION OF POLICY BRIEFINGS

Each instrument was summarised by a member of the consortium who knows that instrument well, is familiar with IDERHA, and therefore, can create a truly expert and highly relevant summary. The task 6.2 leaders began this process by summarising six relevant instruments. These structured summary examples were used to define and communicate the overarching style of summary and use of the template to other members of Task 6.2. Besides this, leaders of other relevant tasks and work package leaders were included in the work. Each member identified topics (nodes or branches) within the topic map on which they could take the lead. In this way, the portfolio of policy briefings was populated through a distributed crowd-sourcing model by domain experts who know the instruments well.

2.3.2 FURTHER REFINEMENT OF THE POLICY BRIEFING TEMPLATE

Following the submission of the initial deliverable D6.1 for Task 6.2 of the IDERHA project, the policy briefing template underwent a revision to address issues raised during the initial data collection phase (this is also reflected in Appendix 1, where there are two different template layouts). The main objective of this process was to improve the template’s clarity and utility by incorporating feedback from contributors and reviewers. The total template collection included in this document is a mixture of the first and second versions of the template. The revised template version has been clarified and made more specific, allowing contributors to provide more focused input. Furthermore, the templates have helped IDERHA to identify critical policy and legislative gaps, as well as cultural and systemic barriers to data sharing. It also provided preliminary areas for the development of recommendations.

2.3.3 POLICY BRIEF TEMPLATE FROM THE SECOND ROUND OF DATA COLLECTION

Template for Gap-analysis task 6.2 IDERHA project
Name of contributor having filled out the template:
Title <i>Example "Dynamic consent"</i>
Potential Problems/challenges/gaps with relation to data sharing in projects like IDERHA
What policies or conditions influence this topic, and how: <i>Example - "national policies, legislation, culture etc., identified in various documents/papers etc."</i>
Suggestions for potential further legislative and policy development to address these potential gaps <i>Example: frameworks, empirical examples</i>
Internal recommendations for the IDERHA consortium <i>Example: Actions that IDERHA can put into practice</i>
Possible areas for further exploration:

2.4 Focus group interviews

The second method of data collection to complete the task's aims was focus group interviews. Focus group interviews offer several advantages, as they help provide rich, qualitative insights, capture diverse perspectives and uncover a profound understanding of participants' attitudes, beliefs, and behaviours through group processes, i.e., discussions and reflections (Thorne 2008, Bernard 1994, Krueger 1994). Focus group interviews are structured and moderated conversations between multiple participants on a specific topic, designed to have a welcoming and non-intimidating setting and elicit both individual and group perspectives on complex topics and questions. Two purposively sampled focus group interview sessions (one for data subjects, one for data holders and data users) were conducted. We conducted the focus group interviews for two different stakeholder groups separately to allow participants to interact on the issues of trust breakdown and mitigations from the perspective of their data role (subject, holder, or user). To balance between the production of robust data and having a small group in which few dominating voices may come to skew results and a larger group being logistically challenging to manage (Bernard 1994), and to ensure international participation, we held online moderated focus group interviews (Schulze et al. 2022, Matthews et al. 2018, Tuttas 2014). As argued by Schulze et al. (2022), online focus groups may yield equally robust data compared to physical focus group interviews if prepared and moderated accordingly.

2.4.1 FOCUS GROUP INTERVIEWS IN PRACTICE

The two focus group interviews were held online and recorded. Focus group 1 had 10 participants, and focus group 2 had 9 participants. Each interview lasted two hours. It was explicitly ensured that all participants could express their opinions and that consensus was not a goal for the interview. Automated transcripts were created based on the recordings that are to be deleted once the work has been published. These transcripts were subsequently used to perform a thematic analysis. For each interview, an interview guide was composed, and a facilitator made sure that all topics from the interview guide were covered.

2.4.2 FOCUS GROUP 1 - DATA SUBJECTS (PATIENT AND CITIZENS)

The primary objective of the initial focus group was to capture the experiences and perspectives of data subjects regarding their fears and concerns related to potential breaches and misuse of their data. This included consideration of deliberate uses by the data holders/users that subjects did not agree to or anticipate, as well as unintended data breaches or disclosures. Participants in this group were encouraged to discuss what specific risks they perceived as the most salient when deciding to allow the use of their data, and the impact these risks could have on their sense of trust and security. Participants considered the impact on their trust in the use of their health data from news stories about data breaches or misuses, whether in the health sector or other sectors such as retail. Additionally, the discussion aimed to crucially explore what kind of mitigating contingency measures participants deem relevant and necessary to restore and promote their personal trust, and public trust in general, if such an occurrence were to happen. By understanding these viewpoints, we aimed to identify effective strategies that data holders and data users could adopt to address and alleviate data misuse concerns.

2.4.3 FOCUS GROUP 2 - DATA USERS AND DATA HOLDERS (ACADEMIA, HTA AND REGULATORY AGENCIES, PRIVATE COMPANIES)

The primary objective of this focus group was to explore the perspectives of data users and data holders in relation to concerns about data misuse, trust, and responsibility. Building on insights from Focus group 1 with data subjects, the discussion encouraged data users to reflect on the risks they perceive in their own data processing and safeguarding practices, and the measures they currently take to mitigate them. Participants considered how they might actively reassure data subjects, either directly or via data holders, in the event of public concerns over poor data practices or breaches, whether in health or other sectors. Additionally, they were asked how they would seek to rebuild trust if their own organisation was responsible for a data-related incident that damaged public confidence.

Additionally, data holders were invited to examine their role in providing assurance and corrective reassurance to data subjects, particularly in their position as intermediaries between data users and data subjects. This included discussions on how they monitor data users' activities, ensure appropriate safeguards, and act in the event of data misuse or breaches. Participants reflected on their responsibilities in fostering trust and considered the practical steps they could take to counteract mistrust, including adopting protective measures suggested by data subjects in the initial focus group. By facilitating this discussion, the objective was to identify collaborative strategies that enhance trustworthiness across the data ecosystem and strengthen the relationships between data subjects, data users, and data holders.

3. Extraction of key themes

As presented in Sections 2.2 and 2.3, Task 6.2 represents an approach to engage with the intricacies of policy gaps within the current landscape of established instruments. This investigation extends not only to those instruments that are already in place but also to those still in development, undergoing revision, or on the brink of final implementation. The objective is to discern the nuanced influence of these instruments on the accessibility and utilisation of data for secondary use. This influence, in turn, influenced the overall scope, functionality, and sustainability of IDERHA and similar data sharing initiatives.

As emphasised, the presented topic map (Appendix 2) served as a visual guide, naming critical areas identified as focal points during the initial stages of this exploration. These critical areas have been pinpointed through an approach that includes an initial review of relevant literature, brainstorming sessions, and engaging in dialogues with experts within and outside the consortium. This initial mapping of topics provided groundwork for a more targeted synthesis of insights.

Through a structured approach of developing a catalogue of executive briefings for IDERHA, key themes have emerged as critical to facilitating access to and reuse of heterogeneous data. The following section synthesises the policy briefing templates in these key themes: 1) Consent, 2) European Health Data Space, and 3) Complying with the EU AI Act. Through these syntheses, key political and legislative instruments relevant to IDERHA are mapped.

3.1 Consent

3.1.1 THE CONTEXT FOR CONSENT

It is well established that the access, use, and reuse of data are highly dependent on trust and thus the willingness of the subjects who provided the data in the first place to share it for secondary purposes. Notable frameworks like the GDPR exist to guarantee that these processes respect and safeguard the sovereign rights of individuals who contribute their data. By emphasising that every use of personal data must have a legal basis and be undertaken with transparency and accountability, the GDPR establishes a formal framework ensuring that data access, use, and reuse are conducted with due consideration for the rights and autonomy of data subjects. Although the use of health data in research might be undertaken through different GDPR legal bases, discussed later in this section, informed consent is frequently used and deserves special examination in the context of IDERHA. Even if IDERHA does not collect new informed consent, some of its data holders may have collected data on that basis and may transfer some obligations in that regard to IDERHA.

The concept of informed consent is recognised as a fundamental and indispensable component, practically ensuring that the access, use, and subsequent reuse of data unfolds with consideration for the individual sovereignty of data subjects. Informed consent in data processes thus ensures that vital decision-making is positioned in the hands of data subjects and promotes a data management environment based on trust and transparency. Since consent is selected as a central aspect of data sharing and data use by consortium experts, consent was decided to be a key theme in this deliverable. Several key consent issues were identified in the early phase of the project. Each topic is presented here with a reference to the relevant template. Templates can be found in Appendix 1.

3.1.2 CONSENT AS A LEGAL BASIS FOR THE SECONDARY USE OF HEALTH DATA

The analysis presented in Template 8.9-8.14 focuses on the legal framework, specifically highlighting the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the AI Act. The analysis in those templates focuses on the exchange and processing of health data in particular. The primary emphasis lies in the GDPR's Article 9.2a, which stipulates the need for voluntary and reversible informed consent. The primary identified gap relates to the issue of getting patient consent to the use of their health data.

As outlined in Template 8.9, consent must be given voluntarily and can be revoked at any time. As a result, it is crucial to ensure that the individual encounters no adverse consequences in the event that they choose not to give their consent initially or later withdraw it. Moreover, concerns regarding the true voluntariness of consent arise from the interdependence and vulnerability inherent in the patient-caregiver relationship. Furthermore, not enough research has been done to establish the degree to which consent may be regarded as freely given in the context of the patient-caregiver relationship. According to GDPR Art. 9.2a and 9.4, consent cannot be implied; on the contrary, a more explicit declaration of consent is required, along with a more detailed description of the processing purposes, as stated in Template 8.13. The notion that there are different interpretations of the GDPR across the European Union complicates matters further and makes handling interjurisdictional research challenging. Moreover, in a research setting, it is impossible to determine processing purposes with the level of precision that is required in the GDPR. Furthermore, processing personal data requires the consent of the data owners, as per GDPR Article 9.2a. As a result, Template 8.10 emphasises the need to create a distinct connection between the act of providing consent and the particular purpose of data processing.

3.1.3 THE IMPORTANCE OF TRANSPARENCY

Template 8.11 emphasises the need to maintain transparency in several areas related to the processing, including recipients, cross-border transfers, purposes, and other relevant information. The degree of transparency must correspond to the person's comprehension. Therefore, to ensure that everyone is aware of the terms of the data processing and can provide informed consent, it is crucial that technical concepts are explained in plain language. Additionally, the importance of Recital 33 of the GDPR concerning scientific research is emphasised in Template 8.12. It is pointed out that, in comparison to the requirements imposed for other processing purposes, the use of Recital 33 to allow Broad Consent implies a lesser degree of specificity and transparency. Broad consent is also seen as an instrument to encourage data altruism in the context of the Data Governance Act. Finding out what level of consent is required is crucial so that individuals have sufficient control over their data.

3.1.4 THE IMPORTANCE OF ADHERENCE TO THE PERMITTED PURPOSE OF USE

Beyond consent, ensuring compliance with GDPR principles necessitates stakeholder awareness and competencies in legal and ethical data sharing and reuse, as outlined in Template 8.1. Given that data sharing risks are highly context-dependent, appropriate frameworks must be developed to align IDERHA's approach with GDPR provisions, specifically Articles 5(1a) and 17.1. This includes safeguards to ensure that personal data is collected for legitimate and explicit purposes, as well as respecting the right to erasure when Article 17 conditions are met. The regulatory landscape highlights the unique status of health data, which is subject to stricter regulations (GDPR Article 9), as well as additional constraints imposed by the European Health Data Space (EHDS) and the Data Governance Act (DGA). These complexities highlight the importance of IDERHA developing strong ethical and legal measures, especially via WP5, to ensure compliance while also allowing for responsible data reuse.

3.1.5 PSEUDONYMISATION

Another significant challenge is pseudonymisation, as discussed in Template 8.2. While pseudonymisation is a critical mechanism for protecting data privacy under GDPR Article 4, inconsistencies in its application across EU member states create significant barriers to cross-border research. The EHDS requires member states to establish health data access bodies in charge of overseeing pseudonymisation practices, but research (Schmitt et al., 2023) shows that variations in national implementations lead to risk-averse approaches that can stifle data-driven innovation. For IDERHA, this disparity in standards complicates efforts to securely access and reuse health data across jurisdictions. A harmonised framework for pseudonymisation, potentially leveraging best practices from organisations such as ENISA, could improve interoperability while remaining compliant with GDPR and EHDS provisions.

3.1.6 ANONYMISATION

Similarly, the issue of anonymisation presents new challenges, especially considering emerging technological developments, as noted in Template 8.3 and Template 8.22. According to the GDPR, anonymised data is not subject to data protection regulations, and the DGA explicitly states that reuse of such data is permitted. However, advancements in de-anonymisation technologies threaten this fundamental principle. Ruohonen et al. (2023) contend that, despite the legal prohibition on re-identification, the increasing sophistication of de-anonymisation techniques may undermine the assumption that anonymised data is permanently untraceable. Anonymisation, a crucial requirement for GDPR compliance, poses challenges owing to the lack of a standardised EU framework, as indicated in Template 8.22. The variability among Member States hinders uniform

application, as indicated in Recital 26 of the GDPR. This calls into question the long-term viability of anonymisation as a data sharing mechanism, as well as the potential need for future regulatory interventions. IDERHA is recommended to implement the utmost data protection standards to mitigate these risks, particularly in international collaborations, and must therefore consider the implications of these technological shifts, particularly in terms of maintaining public trust in data reuse and ensuring that its anonymisation practices remain resilient to evolving challenges. More research is needed to determine whether existing GDPR and DGA formulations are adequate to address these concerns or if additional safeguards will be required to protect privacy in a rapidly evolving digital landscape.

3.1.7 THE ROLE OF OTHER GDPR LEGAL BASES

In addition, Template 8.14 emphasises that processing sensitive data in situations other than gaining consent is allowed under Article 9 of the GDPR. These situations include legitimate interest (9.2.d), public interest in the field of public health (9.2.h), availability of health or social care, handling or administration of health or social care systems and services in accordance with Union or Member State law (9.2.i), and public interest in scientific or historical research (9.2.j). There are significant differences in how these are applied amongst Member States. For-profit and non-profit organisations are subject to different regulations, which are best illustrated by the contrast between private practices and public institutions. Some nations have passed laws pertaining to data management, such as the necessity of obtaining consent from the applicable Data Protection Authority (France, in the case of genetic data, for example). The advancement of inter-jurisdictional research is hindered by the existence of national laws that impose additional limitations on top of the wider EU legislation. The absence of precise definitions for intermediary situations, like public-private partnerships, casts doubt on the existence of particular legal justifications, like the public interest.

3.1.8 DYNAMIC CONSENT

For future consent models, template 8.25 explores the concept of dynamic consent, a flexible approach that could benefit data sharing initiatives such as IDERHA. Dynamic consent allows data subjects to continuously update their permissions over time, as opposed to traditional “static” consent, which terminates all further processing based on that consent upon withdrawal. This adaptable model gives data subjects ongoing control, promoting empowerment over their data use. However, this adaptability adds significant legal and technical complexity. For example, implementing dynamic consent necessitates strict compliance with GDPR principles of lawfulness and accountability, as well as continuous verification of a valid legal basis for processing. This is consistent with the GDPR’s “Privacy by Design” mandate (Art. 25 (1)), which emphasises that technical and organisational measures must effectively protect data subjects’ rights.

Furthermore, Template 8.25 emphasises that designing a compliant dynamic consent system is difficult because it must account for the changing nature of consent within existing legal constraints. Moreover, this model may increase the workload for data holders (who are typically the Data Controllers as defined by GDPR), who must navigate a landscape of variable and unpredictable data sharing preferences. Given the voluntary and revocable nature of consent, any statutory changes to this model should prioritise clarity, consistency, and predictability to prevent fragmentation. Harmonised application across the EU is critical to avoid disparities in standards from national Supervisory Authorities, which could otherwise undermine cross-border data sharing efforts.

3.1.9 THE NEED TO REDUCE LEGAL UNCERTAINTY

As a result, Template 8.25 points out that IDERHA could consider advocating for standardised EU-wide guidelines to ensure consistency and reduce legal ambiguity. By encouraging interdisciplinary collaboration, the consortium may also support initiatives that streamline the consent process while balancing transparency and practical user engagement. Furthermore, investigating the possibility of a harmonised statutory research exemption across the EU could address some of the complexities of dynamic consent, allowing for responsible health data processing while reducing legal burdens on both Data Subjects and Data Controllers.

3.2 European health data space

The changing regulatory environment of the European Health Data Space (EHDS) significantly impacts IDERHA’s operational framework. According to Template 8.21, the principal challenge is to ensure that IDERHA’s Data Sharing Agreements (DSA) comply with both EU and national regulations. This entails aligning GDPR interpretations and establishing pseudonymisation standards to develop a more uniform compliance framework among Member States. Engaging with EU initiatives like European Federation for CAncer IMages (EUCAIM) and European Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) is recommended to gain essential insights into navigating this regulatory complexity.

3.2.1 CONFIDENTIAL COMMERCIAL INFORMATION

The safeguarding of Confidential Commercial Information (CCI) and trade secrets presents further challenges for IDERHA, as indicated in Template 8.20. Achieving equilibrium between transparency and the protection of CCI is crucial, especially considering EHDS's focus on facilitating data access for secondary use to drive health sector innovation while ensuring confidentiality safeguards (Art. 33.4). IDERHA would therefore benefit from establishing a definitive framework for delineating CCI boundaries, ensuring compliance while accommodating instances where secondary data uses deviate from the original intent.

3.2.2 INTEROPERABILITY

The interoperability of IDERHA's federated infrastructure within the EHDS framework is a central aspect, as emphasised in Templates 8.17 and 8.18. IDERHA's federated model necessitates clearly articulated protocols for integration with current EU data sharing frameworks. The existing EHDS guidelines do not provide explicit instructions for linking to private or external sources, as exemplified by the Finnish framework, which limits data access to certified Secure Processing Environments (SPE) through national regulations. Developing a robust interoperability framework for authorised participants and SPE is essential for efficient cross-border data sharing in compliance with both EHDS and national standards, the requirements for which are being developed by TEHDAS2.

3.2.3 SECURE PROCESSING ENVIRONMENTS

Moreover, Template 8.16 emphasises the role of SPEs as secure areas for data access and analysis within the EHDS. In accordance with the Data Governance Act, SPEs must comply with GDPR and generally align with ISO/IEC 27001 standards. Article 50 of the EHDS requires that SPEs comply with minimum data privacy and security standards throughout the EU. To achieve this, IDERHA's federated SPE could implement the Five Safes reports' framework while continuously tracking updates to SPE requirements.

3.2.4 DATA QUALITY

Data quality and completeness are crucial for the effective utilisation of secondary data, as highlighted in Template 8.15. Articles 55 and 56 of the EHDS regulation mandate national Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs) to uphold metadata catalogues that specify dataset quality and scope, in addition to quality labels for publicly funded datasets. IDERHA is recommended to monitor the approach to data quality and utility labelling being defined in the QUANTUM project, through its overlapping partners, which is anticipated to implement these quality labels by 2026, to synchronise its metadata standards with the evolving EU data catalogue requirements, thereby enhancing the discovery, availability and reliability of data in cross-border scenarios.

3.2.5 DATA STANDARDISATION

The implementation of Common Data Models (CDMs) presents additional considerations for IDERHA, as indicated in Template 8.19. Although CDMs enhance interoperability and facilitate data integration, they necessitate substantial initial investments, system reconfiguration, and meticulous data migration to prevent information loss. Implementing CDMs necessitates personnel training and the resolution of potential quality concerns to guarantee that the data managed by IDERHA remains consistent, accurate, and responsive to changing data sharing requirements.

Ensuring robust data provenance and lineage mechanisms is critical for complying with data sharing agreements, as described in Template 8.7. To comply with regulatory requirements and ensure transparency, IDERHA must keep detailed records of data origin, curation, and transformation processes. The use of standard metadata attributes, such as data classification, permitted uses, and de-identification status, can help to streamline compliance and reduce legal ambiguity. Alignment with industry standards, such as ISO 27001, NEN 7510, and TEFCA, would strengthen IDERHA's data governance framework. Furthermore, IDERHA could investigate automated data cataloguing solutions to improve traceability and ease compliance with GDPR Article 30 requirements for data processing records.

The variety of data types necessitates a structured approach to standardisation, as emphasised in Template 8.8. IDERHA must accommodate both structured data (such as EMR and device telemetry data) and unstructured data (such as medical imaging and surgical videos), necessitating the use of multiple data transfer protocols, including HL7 FHIR, CCD, and DICOM. To ensure compatibility across data sources, a Common Data Model (CDM) tailored to lung cancer research could be an efficient choice. It would be beneficial for IDERHA to collaborate with data partners to assess the adoption of the current data format and the feasibility of moving to a unified CDM. This transition, while resource-intensive, would improve interoperability and allow for more advanced data analysis.

The EHDS Regulation requires that patient-level data shared through MyHealth@EU follow the European Electronic Health

Record Exchange Format (EEHRxF), as described in Template 7.6. Although EEHRxF is presented as a recommendation, its implementation will become a requirement for cross-border data exchange. While IDERHA's primary focus is on the secondary use of lung cancer health data, leveraging the EEHRxF format could improve standardisation and data interchange. A modest expansion of EEHRxF could improve its applicability, possibly necessitating a formal recommendation for refinement within the EHDS framework (which could be communicated by IDERHA to the xSHARE and xtEHR projects).

3.2.6 GDPR COMPLIANT AGREEMENTS

Protracted legal and ethical approval processes pose a significant risk to projects like IDERHA's research timelines, as identified in Template 8.26. The need for joint controller agreements and ethical board approvals frequently causes delays in data access, impeding the timely completion of research deliverables. To mitigate these risks, projects like IDERHA should prioritise the completion of its Data Management Plan (DMP) and begin negotiating joint controller agreements as soon as possible. Policy recommendations should call for a more streamlined regulatory framework that strikes a balance between data protection and research efficiency. Furthermore, the availability of standardised templates for joint controller agreements may reduce administrative burdens and accelerate approval timelines.

3.2.7 OVERALL IMPLICATIONS

As a result, aligning Europe's big health data platforms, such as IDERHA, with the EHDS regulations, anonymisation protocols, and interoperability standards is critical for moving forward with data sharing. The incorporation of EEHRxF for structured data exchange, enhanced data provenance mechanisms, and standardised data formats will be pivotal in ensuring compliance and interoperability. Furthermore, addressing delays in data sharing processes through proactive regulatory engagement and process optimization will be crucial in maintaining research momentum. Emphasising the significance of a proactive, coordinated strategy in domains such as SPE integration, CCI safeguarding, and data quality assurance. Continuous legislative oversight and strategic alliances with EU initiatives will be crucial to address existing deficiencies, enhancing IDERHA's capability for cross-border health data research within the EHDS framework.

3.3 Complying with the EU AI Act

A crucial component of IDERHA is to integrate AI/ML Algorithms towards the application of different steps along the Lung Cancer (LC) patient care pathway. Moreover, IDERHA works to further develop dedicated AI/ML algorithms for diverse purposes such as: Personalised LC risk profiling using multimodal data, Personalised AI/ML supported diagnosis of LC using CT scans, Personalised LC prognosis using multimodal data sources (exploratory task), and Health status monitoring and engagement of patients using wearable devices and digital application, in at-home environment

3.3.1 THE APPLICABILITY OF THE EU AI ACT TO PROJECTS LIKE IDERHA

Projects like IDERHA, which are utilising AI algorithms to increase possibilities for strengthened prevention and patient treatment pathways, must conform to the new European Union Artificial Intelligence Act (EU AI Act) in the future. The EU AI Act sets forth a comprehensive regulatory framework to govern the development, deployment, and use of artificial intelligence (AI) across the EU by 2026. This legislation aims to establish strict guidelines and standards for AI technologies, addressing both their benefits and potential risks to individuals, society, and the economy.

Even though the legislation has been passed, it will not officially come into effect until 2026, and therefore, it will not directly influence projects like IDERHA, which is currently developing its AI. However, the EU AI ACT, among other things, categorises AI systems by risk level, implementing stringent regulations on "high-risk" applications, such as those used in healthcare, while maintaining lighter regulations on lower-risk technologies. The IDERHA use cases will be high risk. As projects like IDERHA continue to evolve, it is therefore essential to develop a sustainable infrastructure by embedding ethical, robust and sustainable practices that align with both current and future regulatory expectations. Ensuring long-term sustainability, not only in terms of compliance but also in fostering trust, transparency, and equitable access, will be key to maximising the societal value of AI-driven healthcare solutions.

3.3.2 THE ACT STIPULATIONS ON DATA SETS USED FOR HIGH-RISK AI SYSTEMS

According to the act, future high-risk AI systems (such as in the case of projects like IDERHA) that make use of techniques involving the training of AI models with data, should meet specific quality criteria that should explicate: the intended purpose of the high-risk AI system, how datasets are relevant and sufficiently representative, that data sets, as far as possible, should be free of error and complete, and that GDPR-defined Special category data should only be processed where necessary e.g., to detect bias and with appropriate safeguards as emphasised in Template 8.24.

Additionally, the AI Act holds that such data sets should also meet criteria for appropriate statistical properties regarding the persons or groups of persons in relation to whom the high-risk AI system is intended to be used and mitigate possible biases in the data sets.

However, the inclusion of data from certain minority groups in AI training could present a significant concern, as anonymised personal characteristics can still be analysed within public AI models due to the opaque nature of AI's 'black box' as described in Template 8.27. Clear legislative improvements could therefore be needed to ensure that personal characteristic data remains protected, preventing its use in AI model training, even when anonymised. It should be considered whether research data protected under GDPR is always fit to be repurposed for AI training, as it could pose risks of re-identification and potential threats to the security of minority individuals and groups.

3.3.3 THE ACT STIPULATIONS ON QUALITY MANAGEMENT

The EU AI Act also stipulates that training, validation, and testing data sets shall be subject to explicit data governance and management practices. This means that design choices, data collection processes, the origin of data, data preparation processing operations, formulation of assumptions, assessment of the availability, quantity, and suitability of the datasets, examination of biases within the data (and measures to mitigate against such bias) should be performed and explicated as emphasised in Template 8.24.

Moreover, as described in Template 8.23, the AI Act requires high-risk AI applications and providers to establish a Quality and Risk Management System, maintain technical documentation, undergo conformity assessments, obtain CE marking, and conduct post-market monitoring to ensure ongoing compliance and safety.

3.3.4 POSSIBLE REGULATORY GAPS

As mentioned in Template 8.23, a medical device that functions as or incorporates an AI system must comply with both the Medical Devices Regulation (MDR) and the EU AI Act, ensuring it meets rigorous standards for safety, effectiveness, transparency, and ethical AI usage within healthcare across the European Union. The AI Act also seeks to ensure AI transparency, requiring organisations to disclose when users interact with AI and mandating robust data management to prevent discrimination and biases. However, as mentioned in Template 8.5, a potential gap concerns the clarity around individual re-dress mechanisms in the AI Act, particularly for those affected by decisions made using high-risk AI systems. As legislation evolves, IDERHA should monitor developments related to civil rights and data access to ensure future alignment.

As highlighted in Template 8.4, the ALTAI checklist serves as a structured, compliance-oriented interpretation of the EU's Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI. It offers a practical framework through which ethical considerations, such as human oversight, user awareness, robustness, bias, and data quality, can be more readily assessed. For projects like IDERHA, this provides a tangible means of aligning development practices with high-level ethical standards. However, the absence of formalised conformance criteria presents challenges in reporting, suggesting a need for the project to either adopt emerging templates or develop its own, in order to ensure consistent documentation of ethical compliance across use cases.

Therefore, in what could best be expressed as a pre-emptive response to potential, albeit not yet encountered, policy gaps related to the EU AI Act, it is crucial that projects like IDERHA take proactive measures. This includes performing impact analysis and gap assessment as projects move ahead and ensuring continuous compliance to alleviate risks of subsequent lacking conformity, continuously analysing cases of AI systems developed under the IDEHRA framework against the data-related requirements of the EU AI Act, performing iterative gap assessments as needed, and considering the requirements during the development process as underlined in Template 8.24.

Utilising consent, compliance with the requirement for a legal basis to process prospectively collected personal data across the IDERHA environment, complying with other legal bases for other retrospective data reuse, aligning data access and other governance measures with the EHDS as far as these are known, and compliance with the AI Act, are all vital to the acceptability and sustainability of IDERHA. The first and third of these areas are being monitored and guided by WP5, through specific tasks that assess risk and define appropriate compliance practices and by WP6 for the second area, which has a task focusing on the EHDS. So far, IDERHA has managed to align its intended design and practices appropriately, although it must be recognised that the SPE model for data set sharing is not ideal for some forms of machine learning and AI development. Federation is not currently well supported in the EHDS secondary use data architecture, but it is of growing importance as a data protection safeguard and an expedient architecture for AI development. IDERHA will feed its requirements and experiences to the bodies developing the relevant EHDS implementing acts.

3.3.5 IDENTIFIED ACTIONS WITHIN IDERHA

Task 6.2, engaging with other WP6 tasks, with the IDAGC and with WP5, has been able to surface the content of these three analysis areas through meetings and discussion, with a view to helping WP5 and WP6 to formulate their internal recommendations and practices.

In conclusion, this section has drawn on key insights from the policy briefing templates, highlighting existing and emerging policy and regulatory gaps relevant to IDERHA. Embedding these insights into a sustainable approach is essential, not only to ensure compliance but also to foster trust, transparency, and long-term impact.

4. Incentives and disincentives to data sharing

Data sharing (which might in practice occur through a variety of data access channels) is a critical success factor for all big data projects and infrastructures. Creating a climate in which data sharing is the norm and is handled respectfully towards the data (set) holder and the data subjects contained in a data set are both vital trust factors for data sharing. The EHDS enforces data sharing through regulation, but other data networks such as IDERHA will need to make data sharing attractive, acceptable and low risk so that a wide range of data sources can be included. Inclusivity is itself important to democratise the data held within or queried by the IDERHA platform, to ensure inclusivity of all categories of data subjects and contexts of data capture. AI development especially needs representative data in order to be applicable to diverse possible adoption scenarios, e.g. for its lung cancer stratifications to be accurate across sub-populations and countries.

Therefore, in addition to the three deep dive areas identified in the previous section arising from the template analysis, data sharing incentives were considered important enough to warrant further study. This focus was ratified by consultation with the IDAGC before proceeding with it.

This section considers firstly the data holder perspective, summarising the key considerations a data holder might have to influence their willingness to share. This topic will be taken forward through a literature study to be undertaken during mid and late 2025.

Secondly, the perspective of the data subject has been examined from the perspective of trust. This topic is especially important since the EHDS Regulation will introduce across all EU Member States the right for patients to opt out of the secondary use of their data. It is therefore timely to examine factors that might incentivise patients not to opt out, and factors that might trigger an opt out decision.

4.1 Data holder incentives and disincentives to share data

Meaningful incentives play a pivotal role as central engines that drive stakeholders' motivation to actively participate in various aspects of the data ecosystem, including data provision, procurement, management, analysis, and utilisation. When seen as optimal, incentives may serve as catalysts, fostering a collaborative and cooperative environment where stakeholders are not only willing but also enthusiastic about contributing to and leveraging the data ecosystem. Contrastingly, a lack of, or uncertainty about, incentives among stakeholders may act as a critical barrier to establishing productive and sustainable data-(infrastructure) and, thereby, its potential benefits. In the literature, several incentive gaps making barriers have been identified among the diverse scope of stakeholders acting in critical functions in a data sharing ecosystem.

Among health researchers, current research emphasises that willingness to share data (ultimately adhering to FAIR principles) may be hindered by a complex arrangement of disincentives: Concerns about uncertain intellectual property protection compound this reluctance, as researchers may fear losing ownership of pivotal insights and being pre-empted by academic competitors. Academic promotion is significantly based on academic publications, which require authorship; publications by others that an academic has enabled by sharing their data is barely recognised. These disincentives contribute to a reluctance to engage in transparent data sharing practices.

Additionally, privacy and protection concerns for participants are crucial to the research process and act as a further deterrent. If not feeling adequately protected and accommodated, researchers may hesitate to share data that involves critical participants whose willingness to participate, or potential withdrawal, significantly influences the nature and success of the ongoing research and future projects. This is especially of concern regarding open data, which is strongly promoted within research communities across all sectors, but challenging to achieve with health data due to the near impossibility of guaranteeing robust anonymisation.

Moreover, the prospect of an increased workload resulting from data sharing (for example investing in detailed data documentation and catalogue maintenance, data set curation and cleaning for sharing, anonymisation), coupled with a lack of adequate funding opportunities to mitigate this burden, serves as a disincentive for researchers already immersed in strenuous research endeavours. The overarching effect is a potential hindrance to the seamless exchange of data in the scientific community (Hughes et al., 2023, Panhuis et al. 2014).

4.2 Retaining the trust of the patients within a data set

To patients, the active sharing of their data can be pivotal in advancing the collective understanding of various aspects, including the aetiology of diseases, the impact of different treatments, effective disease management strategies, and the optimal regulation of healthcare expenditures (Kalkman et al 2019). Motivation to participate may come from such considerations as wanting to advance health care in general acting for a the common good (see e.g. Stockdale et al. 2018, Shabani et al. 2014), return incurred benefits, or out of hope of reaping potential future personal health care benefits (Kalkman et al. 2019, TEHDAS 2023b). Nevertheless, it is well established that the lack of willingness of individuals to contribute their data may often be intricately tied to several disincentivizing conditions. These include a lack of transparency, controllability, understanding, and awareness of data use. These conditions ultimately produce a distrust that may hinder willingness to share data.

A recent report from the TEHDAS Project (2023b) provides several recommendations to support data altruism and incentivize data sharing to counter some of the challenges described (in the context of EHEDS). These include (not an exhaustive list) on a policy level establishing and strengthening data-literacy and public awareness initiatives, identifying and adopting relevant business models, specifically for altruism organizations providing mechanisms to ensure recognition of data, providing feedback mechanisms showing how data was used and how data has resulted in benefits (for further elaboration see TEHDAS 2023b). In continuation, it is well-established that sharing data with for-profit companies or projects aimed at financial profits may act as a disincentive for some patients or citizens as they are believed to contradict personal altruistic values. Finding ways or frameworks to mitigate the conflicting values of patients may be important if health research to benefit patients and society is to include the resources and competencies of for-profit companies (TEHDAS 2023b).

A critical driver for advancing data access is to foster improved conditions for transferring knowledge and support environments for joint innovation. However, despite mutually wishing to benefit public health, for-profit companies' additional aims of generating profits may challenge public-private collaborations regarding how research is accessed and used (OECD 2020). Acquiring and analysing data commands significant financial investments. Financial commitments are shared among public health organizations and for-profit companies, regardless of their profit orientation. However, the landscape becomes more complex when examining the context of for-profit companies. Much like the researchers mentioned earlier, for-profit companies face additional complexity in the form of uncertainty surrounding intellectual property protection. This uncertainty may pose a critical disincentive for for-profit companies, introducing a cloud of ambiguity that hampers the clear pathway toward profit realization commensurate with the substantial investments made. To for-profit companies, the interplay between the need for robust intellectual property protection and the imperative to share and collaborate in data-driven initiatives may result in collaborations that inherently carry a risky profile and act as disincentive. Moreover, such challenges to public-for-profit collaborations may be further exacerbated by patients views on for-profit incentives (see above). In this context, it is critical that individuals perceive real and equitable benefits from how their health data is used, especially when private companies are involved. Promoting data solidarity necessitates ensuring that patients and the public receive transparent and equitable returns from data use.

It is, therefore, crucial to understand, accommodate, align, or even mitigate conflicting incentive structures with the various stages of the data lifecycle, cultivating a data-centric culture where stakeholders are not only willing but also eager to participate in activities related to data provision, procurement, management, analysis, and utilization. This process will, in turn, contribute to the overall success and effectiveness of the data ecosystem.

4.3 Exploring trust-building measures through the lens of breakdown

We have investigated initiatives to establish public trust in secondary use of health. To ensure that knowledge of initiatives depart in evidence from concrete real world experiences this investigation takes an oppositional approach focusing its examination on specifically identifying and describing cases where trust broke down ('Trust-breakdowns' - studying what catalysed the breakdown) in projects departing in secondary data (if possible) and thus with relevance for IDERHA, and secondly what kind of trust building initiatives and mechanisms were developed to alleviate the breakdown.

Our research into trust issues is driven by the aim of understanding its relationship to the secondary use of data in projects like IDERHA. We very specifically take a methodological stand of approaching trust from a somewhat binary oppositional perspective, looking at both frameworks that have proved to promote trust and conversely approach 'trust-breakdown' cases (secondary data-case projects in which mundane or extraordinary circumstances have resulted in stakeholders explicating feelings of mistrust, lack of trust, or low trust to name a few conceptual ways to understand trust-breakdowns) as a form of inquiry to understand concrete experiences of trust or lack thereof from cases with the aim of learning and guiding IDERHA. However, it should be noted that we also acknowledge that issues of trust and mistrust are highly complex and, following broader studies of trust in data, (see, e.g., Steadman et al. (2020), Pink et al. (2018), and Dutton and Shepherd (2006)), that people's understanding of an inclination to trust or not may operate in opaque and complex infrastructures often depending on their personal and social experiences in ways that far supersede binary oppositions. However, by still focusing our attention on cases where trust in data sharing initiatives has broken down, we argue that such routes may take us towards conclusions that may very readily show how scepticism or mistrust and trust may live in a dialectic relationship (Steadman et al. 2020, Ramirez-i-Ollé 2018a, 2018b). What we propose is that by exploring contingency measures that prevent or respond to trust breakdowns, we are afforded a view into the kinds of complex forms of scepticism that, if analysed and maybe formalized, may act as a robust engine for the continuous building of trustworthiness of a project like IDERHA.

Based on current debates and academic research, it is essential to consider issues of trust and mistrust in data sharing when addressing the potential policy gaps in utilising health data for research and development purposes. A significant body of literature has already focused on this issue and elicited knowledge demonstrating what may establish and promote trust in various healthcare projects that rely on the collaborative use of secondary data (Hutchings et al. 2020, Cumyn et al. 2023). When providing insights to establishing and promoting trust in such collaborations, there is a general tendency towards identifying and developing trust guidance measures with a preventive-protection focus.

However, how can trust be established in a complex system where it is difficult to predict all possible outcomes and where the possibility of negative outcomes therefore should be included in possible future scenarios? Numerous research studies suggest that trust is built through consent (Biasiotto et al. 2023) and transparency (Hutchings et al. 2020), which, among other things, entails clearly communicating the intended and prohibited uses of data, as well as the measures implemented to protect it from potential misuse. This is also evident in how the GDPR mandates that all data subjects must comprehend and actively assert their position regarding the utilisation of their data. Studies by Benevento et al. (2023) exemplify how an overall increase in health data literacy may act as positive trust-stimulant increasing data subjects willingness to share their data for various purposes. According to Tully et al. (2018), increasing information about how data is used generally encourage people to share their data. However, their research also revealed that in certain cases, these efforts can have the opposite effect and decrease individuals' willingness to share data, despite increasing their health data literacy. Other studies have aimed to expand perspectives on the extent of communication that can contribute to improving trust in data sharing initiatives. From the perspective of data subjects Cumyn et al. (2023) found it essential to deliver both generic and specific information. Generic information includes details about governance and regulatory frameworks, safeguards measures, scientific objectives, and potential future uses of the data. Specific information, on the other hand, pertains to individual data usage, results, and the possibility of data breaches. Different information strategies are beneficial for each type of information. According to Gille et al. (2022) it is crucial to acknowledge that trust building initiatives are to be perceived as iterative programs and demand an ongoing engagement with data subjects to ensure that trust is continuously sustained.

One of the many important factors in establishing trust is the implementation of strong anonymization practices. Benevento et al. (2023) emphasise the importance of anonymization and privacy as the foundation for data sharing. Individuals are more likely to share their data and trust the practice of data sharing when their data is anonymized. However, it is important to recognise that creating a completely secure system is unlikely, and data leaks may still occur in some cases. Even when data is anonymized, people are unwilling to share their information for all research purposes. They will only do so if there is a clear ethical intent behind it. Individuals are concerned about their data being used against their interests in a variety of settings, including insurance companies (Rojas-Avila et al., 2023).

These challenges resonate with broader tendencies. Despite significant advances in implementing data protection measures and informational work to establish trust, data breaches and intended or non-intended data misuse continue making headlines (eg. Forsyth 2024, Gronholt-Pedersen 2016). The relationship between trust and mistrust is widely acknowledged to be highly complex. This is supported by studies on trust in secondary use of data, such as those conducted by Steadman et al. (2020), Pink et al. (2018), and Dutton and Shepherd (2006), which show that people's perceptions of their tendency to trust or not operate in opaque and complex infrastructures often depending on their personal and social experiences. As argued by Gille et al. (2022) trust is shaped by various emotions and different forms of knowledge. Sometimes trust or mistrust building experiences may far supersede individual projects, operating on more general trust or mistrust levels (Hutchings et al 2020). Experiences of breakdowns in projects relying on crucial sensitive health data, whether through personal experience or through news reports, can lead to a lack of trust in collaborations that involve sharing such sensitive data. According to studies by Muller et al. (2022) data subjects highlighted how governance frameworks should include a demarcation of boundaries for use and importantly concrete measures when such boundaries are crossed.

5. Anticipating trust breakdowns

Data subjects may provide consent to the data holder as the legal basis for the latter to hold and reuse their data. This consent is an indication of trust that their data will be held securely, that their identity will be protected and that the uses of their data will be ethical. In other situations, patient data has been captured for healthcare and is then provided within an anonymised data set for reuse. Since anonymisation can be hard to achieve robustly, data holders and data users ought to retain an accountability to the data subjects to safeguard their data. It was decided to examine this trust critically in situations in which the trust may have been broken or threatened by data disclosures, near misses or worrisome (unconnected) data breaches in the news.

Currently, and to the best of our knowledge, most studies and frameworks on trust-building in collaborative projects that involve data sharing and secondary use of data have not given much attention to “anticipated breakdowns” and the establishment of a pre-breakdown framework. This framework would consist of contingency measures that can be used to rebuild trust when it breaks down. This research aims to study what happens when trust breakdowns occur, what catalyse them, how they are perceived and negotiated by stakeholders, and how they are mitigated in post-breakdown scenarios. However, our specific aim is to transition from insights gained after a breakdown to establishing a framework that recognises the interconnected and potentially productive relationship between mistrust and trust (Steadman et al. 2020, Ramirez-i-Ollé 2018a, 2018b). Through the analysis of worst-case scenarios and thereby extreme cases (Flyvbjerg, 2006) of fear for data security breaches and misuse, our aim is to create a blueprint for proactive mitigation measures. This blueprint will help promote trust by anticipating inevitable breakdowns and acting accordingly.

To identify potential gaps in data sharing, we analysed trust breakdowns by reviewing existing literature, presented in the previous section, which examines trust-related factors in the secondary use of health data. Additionally, we conducted focus group interviews with a diverse array of stakeholders, the findings of which will be presented in this section, to obtain valuable insights into their perceptions of worst-case scenarios. This will allow us to better understand the factors undermining trust and serve as the foundation for our investigation into policy gaps associated with the secondary use of data. Furthermore, it will serve as a blueprint for developing recommendations that prioritise trust as the foundation for sharing health data.

5.1 Synthesis of focus group interviews

The following sections presents a synthesis of the key insights gathered from the focus group interviews. The findings highlight recurring themes, shared experiences, and notable differences among participants’ perspectives. By drawing together these diverse viewpoints, the synthesis aims to provide a clearer understanding of the core issues discussed.

5.2 Minor data breaches and social mistrust as a barrier

Despite the increasing prevalence of data sharing initiatives in healthcare research, communication about minor data breaches remains underdeveloped, often reactive, and insufficiently transparent. Trust, however, is not a static resource to be safeguarded only in times of crisis, it is continuously negotiated, particularly at points of vulnerability. Minor data breaches, such as human error, platform mismanagement, or inadvertent disclosure, serve as critical diagnostic events, revealing where communicative infrastructures are fragile or absent altogether.

From the data holder's perspective, minor breaches were often described as "part of the life cycle of data management" and largely as the result of human error: "I had a spreadsheet, and I sent it to the wrong person... these things happen all the time. There is no company where that has not happened to" [2]. While this framing normalises error, it also risks diminishing the perceived importance of communication following such events. This is compounded when organisations fail to notify individuals promptly and transparently. One participant recalled being notified of a breach in vague terms: "It wasn't clear. Or at least it wasn't stated, on whether my information had been affected or not. And I think the lack of transparency on that communication was intentional" [2]. This avoidance of transparency conveys a sense of cover up to data subjects, after which late transparency can be mistrusted.

This experience resonates strongly with those articulated in the citizen and patient focus group, where data breach communication was frequently associated with suspicion and disempowerment. Participants emphasised the relational consequences of poor communication: "I don't want this company to use my data... I'm still angry about something that happened ten years ago, and they have not apologised for it" [1]. Mistrust in these contexts is not necessarily irrational, it is anchored in affective memory, in the perception of patterns of concealment, and in the absence of apology.

Indeed, apology has emerged as an important mechanism of repair. Practically, data users and holders acknowledged this by stating that an apology helped them manage problems. Articulating it in writing, taking swift action, and limiting it to a single apology rather than multiple ones helped to establish trust [2]. However, as citizen participants noted, the apology must be accompanied by institutional recognition of harm and robust mechanisms to ensure that it will not happen again. "We would have to know, you know, basically most everything. Who, what, for how. ... And I should be able to make emotional or not-so-rational decisions," one patient representative insisted [1]. Participants wanted the apology to come from the body holding their data, not via a legal firm or third-party communications company.

When patients/citizens are not consulted or informed about data breaches, mistrust deepens. The failure to differentiate between levels of data sensitivity and the general communication strategies used in response to breaches contributes to the perception that institutions are not acting in good faith.

The absence of meaningful platforms for engagement was cited as a barrier by both groups. A data user reflected, "I don't think we typically get close to the public" [2]. On the other hand, patients expressed frustration with the lack of linguistic, cultural, and educational accessibility: "Will I have it [the apology or explanation of what happened] in my native language? What if I'm dyslexic? What if I'm if I'm blind, is it actually written in a way so that I can understand it? Or did we have lawyers and researchers write it so it's understandable?" [1].

These insights point to the necessity of a pre-breakdown communication framework, a structure that anticipates inevitable failures and offers clear, consistent, and ethically grounded responses. This includes standardised protocols for informing affected parties, co-designed informational materials that account for different literacy levels, and public-facing commitments to transparency. As one data holder noted, telling people what has not happened is an important part of this conversation, and that is how you can reassure and create trust [2]. This might, for example, mean reassuring people that their data is not involved in a breach that has had high-profile visibility. Given these concerns, involving patient or patient representatives from the beginning in health data governance decisions was deemed critical for establishing trust and ensuring that emerging systems, such as AI tools and cross-border infrastructures like IDERHA and the EHDS, are based on patients' needs and values.

5.3 Organising a standard balanced - Balancing particularity and standardisation in mitigation strategies

Organising relevant mitigation strategies that meet the needs of patients/citizens was mentioned as an integral part of data holder responsibility when data breaches occur. As seen in the previous section, delivering transparent responses such as acknowledging the breach and apologising while concurrently demonstrating responsibility for and willingness to accommodate further actions serving patients' needs may act as an engine for trust building. One participant said: "Trust is the result of, I would say, transparency and accountability and transparency, also meaning addressing people, subjects in a manner that is efficient for them, incurring their needs." [2].

The participants in both focus groups agreed that data breaches demand relevant mitigation frameworks. However, establishing such frameworks requires specific considerations.

The participants in the data holder and data user focus group emphasised that they currently often saw mitigation as highly individualised, and lacking an agreed-upon set of rules for mitigation, acknowledged by both patients/citizens and data holders and data users, that could serve as the foundation for further actions when experiencing breaches.

One participant said concerning such fragmentation and a need for shared rules: "Having something to point to say this is this is what's agreed is the way to do things, can carry a lot of weight (...) rather than well, this is what we think is the right thing to do under the circumstances." [2].

To address the risks associated with fragmented responses, some participants in the data holder and data user focus group underlined the establishment of shared standards or a unified code of conduct for research and use of data, which could also act as a standard for mitigation strategies, could be a natural next step. Such a framework should ultimately be developed collaboratively between data subjects, data holders, and data users, ensuring that it is responsive to the rights and needs of data subjects, showing "commitment" [2] while still being manageable by holders and users. As underlined by the participants, a more standardised approach to data use and protection could help promote consistency, transparency, and fairness, which would also help to decide how to act in post-breach interventions, thereby helping to rebuild trust and reinforce accountability across the data ecosystem.

One participant said, "I think having that kind of a model. Like these are the standards, and then you know, these are the bullet points. 1.3 of the of the standards requires you to do XI [...] But going into the usespace, especially when you're talking about scientific research, I think there, are arguments to say, there should be like a code of conduct with a set of, specified standards. These are the kind of within-the-lines kind of conduct and outside-of-the-lines of conduct." [2].

However, developing standard rules for research or a shared code of conduct that could serve as a basis for mitigation strategies was also seen as facing several challenges. As emphasised in our focus group interviews, the development of a standard or code-of-conduct, comprising aligned standards to be adopted by both data holders and data users, could entail the risk of becoming overly standardised and abstract in an effort to satisfy a broad range of institutional stakeholders. Even though inclusivity and broad applicability are important, the participants saw a significant risk that excessively generalised guidelines could lead to superficial implementation. In such cases, compliance with a standard could run the risk of becoming formalistic exercises that would be perceived more as obligations to fulfil than as genuine efforts to respond to the harm experienced by data subjects.

One participant said: "My concern would maybe be that it could lead to a formalism" [2]. This could result in a "tick-box" approach, where compliance could become prioritised over meaningful engagement, ultimately undermining the purpose of mitigation itself.

An additional gap was therefore viewed to be of significant importance by both the participants in the Patient focus group and the Data holder and Data user focus group, and this was related to the issue of adequate or just connections between misuse experiences and relevant forms of mitigation. Current practices for mitigation were expressed as highly context-dependent, meaning that guidance and support were typically tailored to specific instances where misuse had already occurred. One participant stated: "It tends to be very contextual and dependent, so it's hard to create general rules, but I think we should all endeavour to have, you know, sort of a framework for thinking about this. If data is of particular sensitivity and it's exposed in a particular way, it probably should be notified. If it's not, then perhaps not. But I think it's hard to get to that just because the facts tend to be so contextual." [2].

Even though contextuality was perceived as necessary by the participants in the data holder and data users focus group, because it would allow for careful assessment of the particularities of each case, including the nature of the data involved, the circumstances of its misuse, and the resulting impact on the rights, freedoms, and interests of data subjects, the quotation also demonstrated how it proved to pose salient challenge to the idea of standards for research and mitigation that could proactively foster trust, through the transparent application of a pre-defined code of conduct.

5.4 Uncertainties in trust-building efforts

Drawing from the focus group interview conducted with representatives of patients and citizens, several key reflections emerged that raised critical trust concerns regarding the evolving nature of health data collection and use. Participants expressed unease about the dual purpose of health data, being collected not only for immediate, individual clinical care (primary use) but also increasingly for broader, often unspecified secondary purposes, including health research and innovation.

One central issue raised was the long-term trajectory of data use, particularly the current and potential future pooling or aggregation of compounded datasets across systems, institutions, or even national borders. Here, participants in the patient focus group underlined how such pooling of data could lead to risks of future re-identification for specifically marginalised groups due to the potential uniqueness of their data. One participant from this focus group stated: "For some groups of data, it might be possible to sort of retrace the original person given the size of the sample or the characteristics which are being asked for in the secondary data." [1]. While potentially beneficial for large-scale health insights, such pooling was perceived to introduce new layers of opacity and risk for data subjects, especially when clear boundaries regarding governance and oversight were perceived as remaining undefined. Therefore, particular attention must be paid to protecting patients from marginalised communities, who may face disproportionate harm if their data is misused, re-identified, or taken out of its original context.

Such concerns were expressed as highly connected to the contextual nature of health data and the implications this had for its secondary use. Participants in the patient focus group here emphasised that the meaning and relevance of such data were closely tied to the circumstances in which it was generated. When used beyond its original context, particularly in secondary or aggregated forms, the integrity of interpretation could be compromised, which the representatives emphasised could potentially lead to adverse outcomes to data subjects' fundamental rights and interests. As emphasised by the participants in the Patient focus group, despite often being presented as a domain of objectivity, data were never produced in a vacuum; instead, they are the products of situated practices in political and cultural spaces.

One participant said: "So I think there is a more of a meta concern as well that that has to be taken into account here as well and not just a practical thing and particularly when it comes to the minorities. I think it's important to remember that this doesn't happen in a vacuum. It's happening in the political context." [1].

In the patient focus group, the identification of sexual orientation was discussed as an example of data in a political context. While the disclosure of sexual orientation could be regarded as unremarkable or socially accepted in one country, participants in the patient focus group expressed concern that public re-identification through linked datasets, particularly in the event of a data breach, could expose individuals to significant risks when crossing national borders. In jurisdictions where non-heteronormative identities are stigmatised, such unintended disclosures could lead to persecution, discrimination, or other forms of harm.

One participant stated: "What if it (data) is, say, exported from Europe, decoded, and then what? Because then definitely in a lot of countries where it's not just the cultural issue with being gay, then it is probably illegal and potentially having a death penalty." [1].

While the consequences may vary across minority groups, the participants in the patient focus group agreed that currently, the rights of minority groups were an issue of concern. These reflections were further shaped and, in many cases, perceived as exacerbated by the participants in the patient focus group by a broader uncertainty surrounding the future trajectory of data use. They here emphasised that, while current uses of health data could appear ethically sound or socially acceptable, the long-term implications remained difficult to predict, particularly as data infrastructures become more expansive and as analytical capacities evolve rapidly. Therefore, it was expressed as a key concern that individuals would be unable to meaningfully anticipate or consent to future uses of their data when such uses could emerge in contexts radically different from those initially envisioned at the point of collection. This unpredictability was seen as especially concerning in light of shifting political

climates, regulatory landscapes, and cultural norms. What was considered protected in one moment or jurisdiction may, over time or across borders, become a source of vulnerability.

The possibility that data might be repurposed or interpreted through changing socio-political lenses was viewed as a structural challenge to data governance frameworks, which often rely on fixed assumptions about consent, risk, and protection. In this sense, the concern was not only about known risks but also about the uncertainty of future harm. These concerns were not framed merely as abstract or hypothetical. Rather, they were seen as urgent and requiring proactive institutional responses in order to safeguard trust in ongoing and future research initiatives grounded in secondary data use. Without mechanisms that acknowledge and address the temporality and contextual fluidity of data usage, participants in the patient focus group warned that public trust in such programs could be significantly undermined, regardless of the intended benefits of the research itself.

Thus, a critical component to participants in the patient focus group was aimed at finding ways to ensure trust in research projects based on secondary use of data, proactively accommodating such risky, albeit also uncertain, adverse ramifications [1].

Even though the focus group interview with representatives of data holders and data users acknowledged this challenge, it also highlighted a complicated gap.

As mentioned in the previous section, tension was identified between standardisation and contextual responsiveness for data holders and data users. The dual requirement, standardisation on the one hand, and contextual specificity on the other, presented a conceptual and operational challenge for proactive mitigation. Whereas reactive mitigation could adapt to the known details of a specific misuse event, proactive frameworks had to be developed in the absence of such information, relying instead on hypothetical or generalised risk scenarios. These challenges become even more complex when considered alongside the concerns raised by the participants in the patient focus groups, particularly those relating to the uncertain and evolving nature of health data use. As highlighted in the previous sections, the potential future pooling of data across systems and borders, the context-sensitive nature of health information, and the unpredictability of socio-political conditions all contributed to a profound uncertainty about how data may be interpreted, repurposed, or even potentially weaponised over time. In such an environment, the development of genuinely proactive mitigation strategies would find itself strained as to how data holders and data users could meaningfully prepare for future risks that were not only currently uncertain but, to some extent, fundamentally uncertain. As one participant uttered, “Addressing uncertainties and being transparent about them is a huge challenge. I think I understand the sentiment where it is coming from, but it would be difficult to implement” [2].

These intersecting challenges thus reveal that proactive mitigation, while crucial for sustaining trust, currently faces gaps in terms of remaining flexible enough to account for both emerging risks and shifting interpretations of harm.

5.5 References

[1] IDERHA Patient and Patient Advocate Workshop on Health Data Use

[2] Focus Group: Exploring Public Trust in Health Data - Strategies for Managing Mistrust Post-News of Data

5.6 Concluding analysis

When developing a code of conduct, there is a risk that data holders and users may find themselves constrained by the very lack of clarity and contextual grounding that such frameworks are intended to address.

These challenges could indicate a need to work towards a balanced framework beyond codes or procedural checklists toward a more reflexive, adaptive form of mitigation governance that remains open to continuous revision, anticipatory in orientation, and grounded in an ongoing dialogue with those whose data are at stake. Proactive mitigation, in this sense, could benefit from the development of anticipatory principles and practices that are sufficiently robust to guide action in a variety of unforeseen local contexts while still remaining grounded in the core ethical commitment to protecting data subjects' rights and interests. However, such frameworks remain to be developed.

Rather than attempting to eliminate mistrust, we propose developing a framework that acknowledges its inevitability and engages it as a productive force. As Steadman et al. (2020) and Ramirez-i-Ollé (2018a; 2018b) argue, trust and mistrust are not oppositional but entangled processes. It would be beneficial to create anticipatory infrastructures that allow for mistrust while also preparing for, responding to, and using it as a prompt for reflexivity and institutional learning.

6. Conclusion

This deliverable has reported on a consolidated analysis of the areas of European regulation, policy and strategy that influence the secondary data reuse landscape on which IDERHA depends in order for it to develop a large-scale platform for insight generation that can advance innovations in personalised and stratified healthcare. This document has presented and summarised that comprehensive landscape of influences and examined various legislative and policy instruments in that landscape, explaining the impact of each on health data reuse. Certain topics have proved to be of high influence, often recurring across multiple instruments, from which deeper dive syntheses have been developed, on consent, on the opportunities from the European health data space, the obligations on data holders to share data within the more complex of incentives and disincentives to share data, and AI Act compliance.

It is clear that GDPR compliant informed consent is difficult to use as the legal basis for processing when establishing a data platform that might in the future support many uses of the data across organisations. It is especially challenging to obtain consent to provide the legal basis when so many data sets of value come from healthcare, in which consent for healthcare use is implied rather than explicitly captured, and therefore there is no formalised consent for secondary use purposes. However, especially when pseudonymised data is required for longitudinal linkage purposes, a legal basis must be determined. Regardless of the legal basis, transparency back to data subjects (collectively if individuals cannot be identified) is an important factor that influences data subject trust and support of secondary uses.

This topic of data subject trust was examined in considerable detail through the focus groups, which highlighted the importance to individuals of being informed quickly and honestly by the data holder of any data breach that has occurred in the organisation relating to research data, whether or not that individual was included in the breach. People did not want to learn that their data might have been a risk through the news or, potentially less accurately, through social media. After a direct apology, the next most wanted action was to be informed honestly about the risk that the exposure places them in, and what is being done to rectify the situation (mitigate the risk) as far as is possible. Compensation was lower down their priorities. Trust building transparency, demonstrably honest and complete honesty, does have the chance of rebuilding trust and reducing the risk of an opt out being exercised.

While quick communication following data breaches is essential, trust in the secondary use of health data is equally dependent on addressing deeper uncertainties concerning evolving political, cultural, and social contexts. Future risks, particularly for vulnerable or marginalised groups, may not be in focus or even foreseeable at the point of data collection, challenging the sufficiency of static codes of conduct. Trust governance must, therefore, extend beyond reactive measures toward the development of adaptive, anticipatory frameworks capable of evolving with societal changes. Without such reflexivity, standardisation may risk becoming a compliance exercise undermining trust. Proactive transparency regarding uncertainty and engagement with emerging risks are critical to ensuring the trust of data reuse initiatives such as that of IDERHA. As part of this, patient or patient representatives should be involved from the beginning in shaping how health data is collected, used, and shared to ensure that platforms like IDERHA, the EHDS, and AI-based tools meet the needs of patients, foster fairness, and build trust.

The topic of incentives and disincentives for sharing data is complex. The major tension seems to focus on the potential for a data user to derive and exploit insights that the data holder would have preferred themselves to make and use, if this capacity and capability existed within their own organisation. This can manifest as commercial competitiveness, or academic reputation and publication competitiveness. There is no easy solution, and more work is needed to consider reciprocity models that might mitigate the disincentives.

The EHDS, to some extent, takes away this issue of incentives and disincentives by mandating data holders to make data sets shareable through Health Data Access Bodies. This will especially be challenging for proprietary data sets that are (mainly from the industry side) connected with intellectual property or trade secrets or (mainly from the public side) constrained by terms of reference to specific purposes or organisational type or which require scientific assessment before the intended analysis plan is approved. Other topics that the EHDS expects but does not (at Regulation level) specify in detail, but which IDERHA can champion is the adoption of suitable data representation standards and FAIR metadata labelling.

This document also highlights the EU AI Act compliance obligations, on which IDERHA is at an early stage. It will, in particular, need to consider how it will demonstrate the quality and representativeness (lack or minimal bias) of its training data.

Task 6.2 is part of work package 6 that contains other tasks, activities and deliverables that will extend the work reported here, to which task 6.2 experts will contribute.

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Appendix 1: Policy brief templates

8.1	GDPR: Stakeholder awareness and competencies for legal and ethical data sharing and reuse	34
8.2	GDPR: Current potential gaps in cross country pseudonymisation of data	36
8.3	GDPR: Anonymization and new technological challenges	38
8.4	AI: Compliance with the AI ethics principles	39
8.5	AI: Regulatory gaps in the AI Act under revision	40
8.6	Interoperability: Recommendation on a European Electronic Health Record exchange format	41
8.7	Data Provenance and Lineage (traceability)	43
8.8	Data Types & Formats	46
8.9	Consent (i) voluntary	48
8.10	Consent (ii) specific	49
8.11	Consent (iii) informed	50
8.12	Consent (iv) broad	51
8.13	Consent (v) explicit for special categories of data	52
8.14	Other legal bases	53
8.15	Health data quality and utility for the secondary use of health data in the European Union - Implications for IDERHA from the European Health Data Space (EHDS) Regulation proposal	54
8.16	Protection of data privacy and security within the European Health Data Space (EHDS) using Secure Processing Environments (SPEs) for data access and analysis	55
8.17	EHDS interoperability with external infrastructures	57
8.18	Unclarity of the access procedure for the developers and tool installation (WiP)	58
8.19	Common Data Models	59
8.20	Protection of Confidential Commercial Information (CCI) & trade secrets	61
8.21	Evolving legal landscape (mainly EHDS)	62
8.22	Anonymization	63
8.23	Regulatory impact of requirements for high-risk AI systems under the EU AI Act	64
8.24	Requirements related to data and data governance under the EU AI Act	65
8.25	Dynamic consent	66
8.26	Delays in Data Sharing	68
8.27	Challenges of diversity and internationalisation in data sharing in health	69

8.1 GDPR:

STAKEHOLDER AWARENESS AND COMPETENCIES FOR LEGAL AND ETHICAL DATA-SHARING AND RE-USE

IDERHA gap analysis policy brief

Name of contributor having filled out the template: Morten Deleuran Terkildsen, Rasmus Mølgaard Hansen, Lotte Groth Jensen

Topic: Stakeholder awareness and competencies for legal and ethical data-sharing and re-use

Instruments or conditions that influence this topic:

Data re-use may not be inherently risky, rather its risks are context dependent. Risk associated with data-sharing and re-use may be closely dependent on several contextual factors including:

- Topical context shifts, in which ensuring that existing rights and obligations defined when data was procured (such as assumptions and expectations implicit to initial topical usage) are not explicated and carried on and therefore no longer applies in subsequent uses.
 - Cultural moral shifts in context in which the procurement and processing of personal data may be legal under privacy law, yet where the shift may give rise to different moral, cultural, and social concerns, leading to potential direct or indirect adverse impacts on individuals or social groups.
-

Insights provided by analysis/recommendations:

- It is crucial to develop proper awareness, understanding of the context in which data re-use occurs to mitigate risks, protecting privacy, maintaining data accuracy, and ensuring legal ethical practices, and prevent challenges to data access.
 - This calls for building stakeholder competencies via adopting responsible and context-aware framework approaches to allow organizations and individuals to legally and ethically leverage the benefits of data re-use while minimizing potential adverse outcomes thus paving the way for data access
-

Sustainability and potential IDERHA impact:

- Such framework approaches need to be developed or implemented for IDERHA to conform with existing GDPR regulation (e.g. Article 5 1.a and 2)

1a. Personal data shall be: collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes; further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes shall, in accordance with [Article 89\(1\)](#), not be considered to be incompatible with the initial purposes ('purpose limitation')

2."The controller shall be responsible for, and be able to demonstrate compliance with, para-graph 1 ('accountability')." (e.g. Article 17 is made possible if not being the case mentioned in article 17, 3)

The data subject shall have the right to obtain from the controller the erasure of personal data concerning him or her without undue delay and the controller shall have the obligation to erase personal data without undue delay where one of the following grounds applies:

1.the personal data are no longer necessary in relation to the purposes for which they were collected or otherwise processed.

(See other Articles such as e.g. article 20 on data-portability)

- Moreover, compliance also needs to take into account the special status of health data (being sensitive data, with stricter regulation than personal data (GDPR Article 9) and have special attention to the individual regulations that further condition or limit data-use (see article 9.3)
- Needs to follow current DGA regulation (i.e. stipulating conditions for the reuse, within the Un-ion, of certain categories of data held by public sector bodies (see. e.g. Article 5)
- Needs to comply with EHDS regulation act (e.g. Chapter IV, notably Articles 33-38)

Possible areas for further exploration:

-
- Explore potential framework experiences from the development of other Data-Legal- ethical frameworks (this could be such frameworks as Data ethics framework UK)
-

Sources

I) [Risks and challenges of data access and sharing | Enhancing Access to and Sharing of Data :Reconciling Risks and Benefits for Data Reuse across Societies | OECD iLibrary \(oecd-ilibrary.org\)](#)

II) [Data Ethics Framework - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](#)

III) [General Data Protection Regulation \(GDPR\) - Official Legal Text \(gdpr-info.eu\)](#)

IV) EU Data Governance act

V) [REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on the European Health Data Space](#)

8.2 GDPR: CURRENT POTENTIAL GAPS IN CROSS COUNTRY PSEUDONYMISATION OF DATA

IDERHA gap analysis policy brief

Name of contributor having filled out the template: Morten Deleuran Terkildsen, Rasmus Mølgaard Hansen, Lotte Groth Jensen

Topic: Current Potential Gaps in cross country Pseudonymisation of data

This topic concerns data-access to reuse of heterogeneous data, focusing on potential interpretational consistency gaps concerning common pseudonymisation standards or potential lack thereof and the implication for cross-country data reuse.

Instruments or conditions that influence this topic:

Example - "national policies, legislation, culture etc., identified in various documents/papers etc."

According to Art.4 in the GDPR 'pseudonymisation' means the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person. (GDPR definitions Art4-5) Pseudonymisation is stipulated as a cornerstone practice to protect natural persons and in their right to the protection of personal data. (rewrite) Ensuring and upholding proper jointly accepted pseudonymisation may thus act as a critical gateway to ensure data-access across member state boundaries.

a.1. GDPR - General Data Protection Regulation

<https://gdpr-info.eu/>

Current Proposal For A Regulation Of The European Parliament And Of The Council On The European Health Data Space
[EUR-Lex - 52022PC0197 - EN - EUR-Lex \(europa.eu\)](#)

Insights provided by analysis/recommendations:

Example - "identified differences in policy, legislation, and culture between EU partners. fleshed out examples"

- EHEDS proposal specifies that "Member States will have to set up a health data access body for secondary use of electronic health data and ensure that electronic data are made available by data holders for data users"
- In terms of pseudonymisation the EHDS further specifies that "Where the purpose of the data user's processing cannot be achieved with anonymised data, taking into account the information provided by the data user, the health data access bodies shall provide access to electronic health data in pseudonymised format. The information necessary to reverse the pseudonymisation shall be available only to the health data access body. Data users shall not re-identify the electronic health data provided to them in pseudonymised format. The data user's failure to respect the health data access body's measures ensuring pseudonymisation shall be subject to appropriate penalties." (EHEDS 43) Meaning that the proposed member state health data access bodies are made responsible for adhering to proper and sufficient pseudonymisation practices.
- However, as stated by Schmitt et al. (2023) lack of consistent EU interpretation of what may constitute issues such as sufficient pseudonymisation has led to diversity and many member-states to adopt risk adverse strategies and cautious practices that may hinder data innovation.

Gaps with potential IDERHA impact:

Example - "Listing of crucial gaps in relation to IDERHA and suggestions for further legislative and policy development to ameliorate these potential gaps"

- It may therefore be profitable to develop and ensure adherence to a common interpretation of proper pseudonymisation practices across state data health access bodies to alleviate potential obstacles to cross country data access.

Possible areas for further exploration:

- Such common formal interpretation approaches could be based on existing work (e.g. ENISA Pseudonymisation techniques and best practices Recommendations on shaping technology according to data protection and privacy) but needs further exploration

8.3 GDPR: ANONYMIZATION AND NEW TECHNOLOGICAL CHALLENGES

IDERHA gap analysis policy brief

Name of contributor having filled out the template: Morten Deleuran Terkildsen, Rasmus Mølgaard Hansen, Lotte Groth Jensen

Topic: Anonymization and new technological challenges

This topic concerns current formulations in the DGA concerning anonymization practices and responsibilities that may be subject to challenge by on-going technological development.

Instruments or conditions that influence this topic:

Example - "national policies, legislation, culture etc., identified in various documents/papers etc."

As highlighted in previous templates, following GDPR guidelines (refers to pseudonymization), issues of reuse and access to data do not fall under GDPR when the data has been effectively anonymized. The DGA's stipulation for granting access to data reuse beyond the confines of GDPR's restrictions is contingent upon the thorough anonymization process. This is underscored in the DGA documentation, where it is stated that:

8) In accordance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679, the principles of data protection should not apply to anonymous information, namely information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person, or to personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable. Re-identification of data subjects from anonymised datasets should be prohibited. This should not prejudice the possibility to conduct research into anonymisation techniques, in particular for the purpose of ensuring information security, improving existing anonymisation techniques and contributing to the overall robustness of anonymisation, undertaken in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679.

In this sense, access to re-use of data falling outside the jurisdiction of the GDPR thus hinges on the provision of robust anonymization techniques (Falling under the responsibility of member state public bodies / competent bodies). So that:

Before transmission, personal data should be anonymised, in order not to allow the identification of the data subjects, and data containing commercially confidential information should be modified in such a way that no confidential information is disclosed."

Moreover Article 5 in the DGA specifies that:

3. Public sector bodies shall, in accordance with Union and national law, ensure that the protected nature of data is preserved. They may provide for the following requirements:

(a) to grant access for the re-use of data only where the public sector body or the competent body, following the request for re-use, has ensured that data has been:

(i) anonymised, in the case of personal data."

Acts and legislation influencing this topic:

a.2. GDPR

<https://gdpr-info.eu/>

DGA

EU Data Governance act

Insights provided by analysis/recommendations:

Example - "identified differences in policy, legislation, and culture between EU partners. fleshed out examples"

- The DGA states that though re-identification is prohibited, such prohibition should not hinder research and development of improved anonymization techniques.

- However, as emphasized by Ruhonen et al. (2023), examples of de-anonymization technologies and techniques already exist, and following current technological trends, the existence of such technologies is expected to increase in the near future. This development raises salient questions regarding its impact on data-access and reuse. These may include (not an exhaustive list)

-Despite its illegality, how does the DGA propose to handle future possibilities for de-anonymization when clear examples of such techniques are on the horizon and their possibilities for compromising anonymization may bring anonymization practices into conflict with the GDPR (even though this is currently not possible as anonymization is seen as removing the opportunity for re-identification) because they can no longer ensure the rights of privacy of subjects as mentioned in the GDPR?

-How do such future scenarios influence public trust in the use and reuse of data and thus their willingness to allow sharing of their data?

Ruohonen, J., Mickelsson, S. Reflections on the Data Governance Act. DISO 2, 10 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44206-023-00041-7>

Gaps with potential IDERHA impact:

Example - "Listing of crucial gaps in relation to IDERHA and suggestions for further legislative and policy development to ameliorate these potential gaps"

- Additional research might be necessary to delve into the potential void that could arise from emerging de-anonymization technologies. More specifically, further knowledge could be needed to explore the emergent gap between GDPR and the rights to privacy and formulations stipulating data-access governance and reuse in the DGA based on anonymization.

Possible areas for further exploration

8.4 AI: COMPLIANCE WITH THE AI ETHICS PRINCIPLES

IDERHA gap analysis policy brief

Name of contributor having filled out the template: Dipak Kalra, Sanziana Negreanu Arboreanu

Topic: Compliance with the AI ethics principles

Instruments or conditions that influence this topic:

- Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, April 8, 2019, High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, European Commission <https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/ai-alliance-consultation.1.html>
 - Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI) for self-assessment, July 17, 2020, High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, European Commission <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence-altai-self-assessment>
-

Insights provided by analysis/recommendations:

The ALTAI checklist is a structured compliance-oriented representation of the Ethics Guidelines, and therefore an easier form in which to verify ethical compliance. The following is a non-exhaustive list of its main topics:

- Human interaction model and decision taking involvement
 - AI user awareness
 - Potential for interference with human decision making
 - Oversight
 - Ability to “emergency stop” the AI from proceeding and taking actions
 - Cybersecurity: integrity, robustness, security, resilience from attack
 - Risk management
 - Reliability and stability testing, fault tolerance, failsafe mechanisms
 - Accuracy of the training data, monitoring of accuracy during use, handling of uncertainty, missing data etc.
 - Continual learning e.g. protection measures against risks of learning from unsuitable patterns, traceability of the learning cycles and the data inputs used
 - Information governance
 - Bias (mostly related to the quality and characterisation of the training and validation data)
 - Accessibility
 - Monitoring for negative impacts
-

Gaps with potential IDERHA impact:

1. At present there is no standardized way by which an AI developer would report conformance to this checklist, because it is presented as a collection of labelled paragraphs, describing each topic but without formal conformance criteria. IDERHA may therefore have to look around for emerging reporting formats or templates or invent its own. In either case, compliance documentation could be relatively burdensome, although important.
 2. Gap assessment within IDERHA project for AI Act requirements for high-risk AI systems is on-going
-

Possible areas for further exploration:

1. To identify emerging good practices in conformity checking and reporting formats, or to create one specifically for the project.
2. To consider working through IHI office to bring together projects tackling AI development in order to agree a consensus conformity checking and reporting method.

8.5 AI: REGULATORY GAPS IN THE AI ACT UNDER REVISION

IDERHA gap analysis policy brief

Name of contributor having filled out the template: Morten Deleuran Terkildsen, Rasmus Mølgaard Hansen, Lotte Groth Jensen, Sanziana Negreanu Arboreanu

Topic: Regulatory gaps in the AI Act under revision - Individual rights in the use of AI for decision-making

This topic focuses on the rights of individuals in terms of development and usage of AI technologies for decision-making policies, as currently stipulated in the AIA, as well as identified gaps and current ongoing EU legislative work to fill such gaps.

Instruments or conditions that influence this topic:

Example - "national policies, legislation, culture etc., identified in various documents/papers etc."

EU Artificial Intelligence Act 2024/1689

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj/eng>

A Critical Assessment by Members of the Robotics and AI Law Society (RAILS)

Ebert. et al (2021)

[|| Free Full-Text | The European Commission's Proposal for an Artificial Intelligence Act—A Critical Assessment by Members of the Robotics and AI Law Society \(RAILS\) \(mdpi.com\)](#)

Insights provided by analysis/recommendations:

Example - "identified differences in policy, legislation, and culture between EU partners. fleshed out examples"

As noted by Eber. et al (2021) the initial draft of AIA did not sufficiently include provisions for individual rights. Despite its aim to safeguard fundamental rights, it fell short in offering avenues for individuals to pursue recourse in case of a violation of the regulation. A call was made to ensure that proper redress mechanisms were formulated and included in later revision. Currently legislative work is underway seeking to strengthen citizens' rights to complain. It is currently stipulated explicitly only as concerning decisions based on High-risk systems that impact citizens' rights.

Gaps with potential IDERHA impact:

Example - "Listing of crucial gaps in relation to IDERHA and suggestions for further legislative and policy development to ameliorate these potential gaps"

Though not currently mentioned as an issue of access to data, the current legislation should be followed as issues of rights to complain could potentially come to include legislation also aimed at limiting potential threats to citizens' rights in the form of data-access legislation.

While the ongoing legislative efforts primarily target high-risk systems, closely monitoring the current legislative process could be advisable. Monitoring the process will help ensure that IDERHA remains in accordance with the civil rights requirements outlined in the legislation should it expand to cover AI technologies in additional risk categories.

Possible areas for further exploration:

Follow the development of the legislative process for the individual rights of citizens when developing new forms of AI-technology

8.6 INTEROPERABILITY: RECOMMENDATION ON A EUROPEAN ELECTRONIC HEALTH RECORD EXCHANGE FORMAT

IDERHA gap analysis policy brief

Name of contributor having filled out the template: Dipak Kalra, Nadja Kartschmit

Topic:

- The EHDS Regulation requirements for interoperability
- Recommendation on a European Electronic Health Record exchange format

Instruments or conditions that influence this topic:

The EHDS Regulation requires that identified patient level data, to be communicated via MyHealth@EU, conforms to the European Electronic Health Record exchange Format (EEHRxF).

https://health.ec.europa.eu/publications/proposal-regulation-european-health-data-space_en

<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/recommendation-european-electronic-health-record-exchange-format>

The EEHRxF was a Recommendation but is now defined under Article 15 of the EHDS Regulation. Electronic Health Record (EHR) systems will be required to be able to export patient level data in the EEHRxF Format. Member State National Contact Points will firstly be required to ensure that cross-border patient level data flows conform to the standard as well as other stipulations in the proposed EHDS Regulation and secondly be required to oversee the conforms to the exchange of EHR systems within the Member State health system.

The EEHRxF should at least cover the following EHR priority categories that must be made accessible and interoperable across Member States (Article 14 and Annex I):

- Patient summaries
- Electronic prescriptions
- Electronic dispensations
- Medical imaging studies and related imaging reports
- Medical test results, including laboratory and other diagnostic results and related reports
- Discharge reports

Member States can add more categories in addition to the above-mentioned.

Additionally, the final EHDS Regulation includes multilingual compatibility (Recital 26).

Regarding the technical specification for the priority categories, the EHDS regulation requires the Commission to issue implementing acts by March 2027 (Article 15(1)).

The EC's MyHealth@EU initiative, that Member States will be required to participate in, has largely developed the technical and governance specifications required to communicate this information between countries. Some countries see this as also useful to adopt internally.

The legal framework for cross-border infrastructure via MyHealth@EU using EHR format is defined in Article 23.

The Commission should regularly update the format via implementing acts (Art. 15(2)).

Insights provided by analysis/recommendations:

IDERHA is primarily undertaking secondary use of lung cancer health data, constructing big data sets for federated analysis, developing AI, personalized decision making and risk stratification tools and implementing a clinical research platform. However, the source data is likely to come from EHR systems that today use heterogeneous data models and implement standards to a variable extent. If, during IDERHA's lifetime, conformance to the EEHRxF grows, this might become a more reliable source data format to leverage. It may therefore be valuable for IDERHA to implement an ETL process feeding its secondary use platform for EEHRxF format data.

Gaps with potential IDERHA impact:

The EEHRxF is being promoted as an EHR representation, but it is in practice limited to a patient summary and continuity of care clinical documents. The laboratory or imaging reports may be the most fruit-ful. We will still find we are missing some lung cancer specific data (certainly no genomics).

Possible areas for further exploration:

1. A gap analysis of data item specification may be a useful first step, in order to determine the utility of the clinical content represented by the EEHRxF to IDERHA.
2. If we find that a modest enlargement of the EEHRxF would increase its utility, this might be recommendation formalized by WP6 and presented to the Council.

IDERHA could recommend technical specifications for the priority categories based on lessons learned throughout the project lifetime.

8.7 DATA PROVENANCE AND LINEAGE (TRACEABILITY)

IDERHA gap analysis policy brief

Name of contributor having filled out the template: LeRoy Ruggerio

Topic: Data Provenance and Lineage (traceability)

Including:

- Origin
- Tagging
- Curation
- Mapping
- Quality/Bias
- Transformations/Linking
- Retention (Archival/Destruction)

Instruments or conditions that influence this topic:

Example - "national policies, legislation, culture etc., identified in various documents/papers etc."

Requirements to keep detailed records of data origin/provenance, cohort, bias and merging, linking, mapping or transformation, etc. of all data assets that are used to develop or that result in any re-search insights, conclusions or models generated.

Insights provided by analysis/recommendations:

Example - "identified differences in policy, legislation, and culture between EU partners. fleshed out examples"

Data inventory and lineage traceability is required to comply with the various terms of any data use agreements that will be in place between IDERHA (as a data processor) and any IDERHA data part-ners or collaborators. Some key areas of compliance that would be governed can include (with agreement metadata attributes):

- Covered Entity / Data Provider / Collaborator
- Contract Type
- Data PHI Status (Y/N)
- Legal mechanism for PHI
- Permitted Primary Use Category
- Permitted Secondary Use Category
- Verification that the source (if signing party is a non-hospital system) has the right to share da-ta
- Data Classification (PHI/PII, Device telemetry data-low risk, Public Data)
- Data Host Platform
- Data Host Geography
- Permitted Storage Geography (restrictions for data transfer to other country/regions)
- Permitted Use Geography
- De-identification using a third party
- De-Identified Data
- De-Identification Method
- Effective Date (Agreement Expiration Date)
- Post Termination Disposition
- Retention Policy / Date
- Consent Date
- Patient Consent - Primary Status
- Patient Consent - Secondary Status

Gaps with potential IDERHA impact:

Example - "Listing of crucial gaps in relation to IDERHA and suggestions for further legislative and policy development to ameliorate these potential gaps"

Current gaps may be a general architecture/plan for the platform and a charter that would identify potential data types, data sources, initial uses anticipated, agreement terms for collaborators, permitted data uses, permitted access, etc.

Some examples of industry standards and certifications are in the table below (in addition to ISO 27001:2022, NIST Cybersecurity Framework and potentially HITRUST):

Source: LeRoy Ruggerio

National Standards-Netherlands NEN 7510

- The NEN 7510 is the official Dutch standard for setting up and implementing information security management systems for organizations working with healthcare patient data. The standard became mandatory for healthcare institutions and providers starting on January 1, 2018, offering further interpretation and accountability under Article 32 of the GDPR.
- NEN 7510 is a set standard, outlining practices and mandatory requirements for processing personal data, with an emphasis on confidentiality and accountability. The NEN 7510, 7512, and 7513 offer additional interpretation of requirements in light of the needs of healthcare providers. It also offers measures and standards to identify risks to ensure the confidentiality, availability, and integrity of secured data. The standards also ensure that data owners can decide what information can be shared, and to which providers.
- Companies are required, by law, to utilize the NEN 7510 in the Netherlands.
- These standards describe measures that must be taken by health care institutions and suppliers. This, in order to protect data of patients adequately. These measures will result in a monitored process concerning information security.

ISO cloud standards - ISO 270017, 270018

- ISO 27017 is the information security best-practice framework for cloud service providers and their customers. It enables them to implement information security processes and procedures to ensure information stored in the cloud is safe and secure.
- ISO/IEC 27018:2019 is an information security code of practice for cloud service providers who process personally identifiable information for their customers.

Trusted Exchange Framework and Common Agreement (TEFCA)

The overall goal of the Trusted Exchange Framework and Common Agreement (TEFCA) is to establish a universal floor for interoperability across the US. The Common Agreement will establish the infrastructure model and governing approach for users in different networks to securely share basic clinical information with each other—all under commonly agreed-to expectations and rules, and regardless of which network they happen to be in. The Trusted Exchange Framework describes a common set of non-binding, foundational principles for trust policies and practices that can help facilitate exchange among HINs

ISO 31700 - Privacy by Design for Consumer Goods and Services

Privacy Embedded into Design, Respect for User Privacy (User Centric), Visibility and Transparency, Full Functionality (Positive-Sum not Zero-Sum), End-To-End Security (Full Lifecycle Protection), Privacy as the Default Setting, Proactive not Reactive (Preventative not Remedial)

IMDRF (International Medical Device Regulators Forum)

IMDRF is a voluntary group of medical device regulators from around the world who have come together to build on the strong foundational work of the Global Harmonization Task Force on Medical Devices (GHTF) and aims to accelerate international medical device regulatory harmonization and convergence.

CMMC (Cybersecurity Maturity Model Certification)

The Cybersecurity Maturity Model Certification (CMMC) is the Department of Defense's (DoD) newest verification mechanism designed to ensure that cybersecurity controls and processes adequately protect Controlled Unclassified Information (CUI) that resides on Defense Industrial Base (DIB) systems and networks.

ISO 13485

ISO 13485 Medical devices -- Quality management systems -- Requirements for regulatory purposes is a voluntary standard, published by International Organization for Standardization for the first time in 1996, and contains a comprehensive quality

management system for the design and manufacture of medical devices.

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SO/IEC 27559:2022

Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection - Privacy enhancing data de-identification framework

NOTE: There are also additional privacy related regulations around protection of data subject rights that apply to both Data Controllers and Data Processors. Depending on the charter and intended use of the data for the IDERHA program, these may

Health Data Sources:

- Hospital EMR Data
- Provider Curated Data
- Medical Devices
- Wearables

Logos: PREMIER, IQVIA, CPDR, NHS, Pharmacies, Healthcare Providers, Labs, Wearables and Devices, HIRA, Pfizer, CDMs.

Data Formats:

- Structured
- Unstructured (Notes)
- Images (DICOM w/Metadata)
- Video
- Audio
- Binary

Data Transfer Protocols:

- CSV
- HL7 (v2, v3)
- FHIR
- CCDA
- XML
- PDF
- CDM
- Binary files

Logos: HL7 FHIR, CSV, PDF.

also apply and would require additional traceability to comply with data subject rights (i.e.- Access and Correction, Right to be Forgotten, etc.)

GDPR Article 30 Clause 2 states:

Each processor and, where applicable, the processor’s representative shall maintain a record of all categories of processing activities carried out on behalf of a controller, containing:

- (a) the name and contact details of the processor or processors and of each controller on be-half of which the processor is acting, and, where applicable, of the controller’s or the proces-sor’s representative, and the data protection officer.
- (b) the categories of processing carried out on behalf of each controller.
- (c) where applicable, transfers of personal data to a third country or an international organisa-tion, including the identification of that third country or international organisation and, in the case of transfers referred to in the second subparagraph of Article 49(1), the documentation of suitable safeguards.
- (d) where possible, a general description of the technical and organisational security measures referred to in Article 32(1).

Possible areas for further exploration:

Explore/Research potential products to help with automation of data inventory and data lineage (provenance across the data lifecycle). There are several data cataloging software products available that can help with traceability of data assets throughout the multiple phases of the data lifecycle. The specific requirements for capabilities would need to be reviewed prior to a product feature comparison. Most data cataloging systems provide the core capabilities required for proper data traceability.

8.8 DATA TYPES & FORMATS

IDERHA gap analysis policy brief

Name of contributor having filled out the template: LeRoy Ruggerio

Topic: Data Types & Formats (what types and formats of data will be the focus of the IDERHA plat-form and research?)

- Data structured according to a fixed schema (e.g. tabular)
 - EMR data
 - Device data (telemetry / use)
 - ePRO - patient experience data
 - Diagnosis
 - Treatment
 - Payment data

 - Data without a structured schema (e.g. video, images, audio)
 - DICOM
 - XRAY/MRI/Ultrasound
 - Procedure video (with or without audio)
 - OR video

 - Data Transfer Protocols
 - CSV
 - HL7 (v2, v3)
 - FHIR
 - CCDA
 - XML
 - PDF
 - CDM
 - Binary files
-

Instruments or conditions that influence this topic:

Example - "national policies, legislation, culture etc., identified in various documents/papers etc."

Requirements for specific research use cases to support research/analytics efforts.

Focus areas here will also guide the data use agreement terms, collaboration terms and partners, data preparation (raw, anonymized, masked, tokenized, etc.) as well as the various analytical tools required to perform the research analysis. This will also help inform the data collection and storage requirements as well as the required capacity and compute resources for the data / analytics platform.

Another requirement that will need to be addressed is that of a defined standard "Common Data Model" to be adopted by the platform for specific disease states/treatments/devices and the data as-associated to each. This will also need to be socialized with potential data collaboration partners to de-terminine their willingness for adoption and transformation work toward the new CDM. This conversion can be quite complex, and time/resource/effort consuming and could be a barrier to entry to the value of the data platform and analytics capabilities.

Some decision factors include:

- Standards adopted by data collaborators (both in format/protocol and CDM)
- Types of data required for research efforts (structured, device, unstructured - video, images, audio)
- Data Transformation assistance - provided to collaborators that may not has adopted a standard in protocol/transport/ CDM as this can be time consuming and costly.
- Types of access and use of final data - how will data be used and analyzed (analytics tools, DB, methods, etc.)
- Will there be a 3rd party integrator that will be processing data feeds and converting to a CDM?

- What data use agreements will be in place with collaborators?
- Will data be collected, aggregated/linked, cleaned, anonymized and transformed to CDM at source or in a central collection point within IDERHA?
- Other decision factors will likely arise concerning legal basis, cost and size of data assets for feasibility of transfer and processing.

Figure 12: source: LeRoy Ruggerio

Insights provided by analysis/recommendations:

Example - "identified differences in policy, legislation, and culture between EU partners. fleshed out examples"

There are several standards for data types, transfer protocols, formats and Common Data Models available. It is highly recommended to identify a target group of data collaboration partners and survey them for what standards they've adopted in these areas and what amount of extra conversion work would they consider for entry into the collaboration network.

Gaps with potential IDERHA impact:

Example - "Listing of crucial gaps in relation to IDERHA and suggestions for further legislative and policy development to ameliorate these potential gaps"

Possible gaps would include:

- EMR systems and standards
- Data format standards
- Transfer protocols
- Anonymization methods to comply with regional requirements.
- Data Protection (access restrictions)
- Data Size and transfer methods / bandwidth requirements

Possible areas for further exploration:

Self-explanatory

Identify requirements and target profiles for Data Network Collaboration Partners and conduct interviews / Surveys to determine their systems and standards for EMR and device data including:

- EMR system(s) vendor
- Common Data Model standard
- Cybersecurity standards and certification requirements for partners (ISO, HITRUST, NIST, etc.)
- Network connectivity / bandwidth
- Supported transfer protocols/formats
- Agreement types for shared data use
- What types of procedures performed (and data available):
 1. General Surgery
 2. Gastrointestinal Surgery
 3. Orthopedic Surgery
 4. Cardiovascular Surgery
 5. Thoracic (Cardiothoracic) Surgery
 6. OB/GYN-related Surgery
 7. Neurosurgery
 8. Ophthalmological (Eye) Surgery
 9. Otolaryngological (ENT) Surgery
 10. Urological Surgery

8.9 CONSENT (I) VOLUNTARY

IDERHA gap analysis policy brief

Name of contributor having filled out the template: Dominik Geller & Maria Bardaji-Cruz

Topic GDPR compliant informed consent

Instruments or conditions that influence this topic:

- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR)
 - Applicable National Data Protection Law (please specify)
 - Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data (Data Act)
 - Other EU or National Laws if applicable (please specify)
-

Insights provided by analysis/recommendations:

For the analysis, please specify on what grounds health data is processed and/ or shared and what differences or inconsistencies you observe in the application of the law vs. literacy EU law, across territories and/or different organizations/ players, or whether it is Processing/ sharing shall be based on the consent (Art 9.2a GDPR), which shall be VOLUNTARY/ WITHDRAWABLE:

- The consent needs to be free, i.e. the individual shall be able to grant it or not without suffering any kind of detriment
 - Position of weakness and dependence vis-à-vis the controller
 - Not dependable on other services
-

Gaps with potential IDERHA impact:

- Patients, as vulnerable individuals, will not always be able to choose freely whether to consent or not, hence there will likely be some considerable level of dependency.
-

Possible areas for further exploration:

- How much consent can be considered freely given in a patient-caregiver scenario

8.10 CONSENT (II) SPECIFIC

IDERHA gap analysis policy brief

Name of contributor having filled out the template: Dominik Geller & Maria Bardaji-Cruz

Topic: Consent (I)- specific (2)

Instruments or conditions that influence this topic:

- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR)
 - Applicable National Data Protection Law (please specify)
 - Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data (Data Act)
 - Other EU or National Laws if applicable (please specify)
-

Insights provided by analysis/recommendations:

For the analysis, please specify on what grounds health data is processed and/ or shared and what differences or inconsistencies you observe in the application of the law vs. literacy EU law, across territories and/or different organizations/ players, or whether it is Processing/ sharing shall be based on the consent (Art 9.2a GDPR), which shall be SPECIFIC:

- Link between the provision of consent and the particular data processing operation
 - Unambiguous
 - Recital 33- relaxed criteria, however not applicable for sensitive data
-

Gaps with potential IDERHA impact:

- Defining the parameters of each processing activity within research is impracticable.
-

Possible areas for further exploration:

- Possibility of defining the level of specificity required in research context

8.11 CONSENT (III) INFORMED

IDERHA gap analysis policy brief

Name of contributor having filled out the template: Dominik Geller & Maria Bardaji-Cruz

Topic: Consent (I)- informed (3)

Instruments or conditions that influence this topic:

- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR)
 - Applicable National Data Protection Law (please specify)
 - Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data (Data Act)
 - Other EU or National Laws if applicable (please specify)
-

Insights provided by analysis/recommendations:

For the analysis, please specify on what grounds health data is processed and/ or shared and what differences or inconsistencies you observe in the application of the law vs. literacy EU law, across territories and/or different organizations/ players, or whether it is

Processing/ sharing shall be based on the consent (Art 9.2a GDPR), which shall be INFORMED:

- Need for transparency in all relevant aspects of the processing, e.g. recipients, cross bor-der transfer, purposes, etc.
 - Adequate to the level of understanding of the individual
-

Gaps with potential IDERHA impact:

- Translating technical matters into lay terms to make sure the individual fully understands the parameters of the data processing
-

Possible areas for further exploration:

- Possibility of defining the information which shall be considered as sufficient in research con-text

8.12 CONSENT (IV) BROAD

IDERHA gap analysis policy brief

Name of contributor having filled out the template: Dominik Geller & Maria Bardaji-Cruz

Topic: Consent (II)- broad

Instruments or conditions that influence this topic:

- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR)
 - Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act)
 - Other EU or National Laws if applicable (please specify)
-

Insights provided by analysis/recommendations:

For the analysis, please specify on what grounds health data is processed and/ or shared and what differences or inconsistencies you observe in the application of the law vs. literacy EU law, across territories and/or different organizations/ players, or whether it is

- In respect of scientific research Rec. 33 GDPR allows for Broad Consent, which level of specificity and transparency is lower in comparison to the one required for other pro-cessing purposes. Broad consent is also considered for data altruism in the Data Govern-ance Act.
 - Does not need to be explicit for sensitive data.
-

Gaps with potential IDERHA impact:

Although the level of specificity and transparency would be lower in this scenario there is still a need to collect a declaration of consent from the individual which in several cases is impracticable.

Possible areas for further exploration:

How much consent is equivalent to sufficient control of the individuals over their data if other con-siderations are not met.

8.13 CONSENT (V) EXPLICIT FOR SPECIAL CATEGORIES OF DATA

IDERHA gap analysis policy brief

Name of contributor having filled out the template: Dominik Geller & Maria Bardaji-Cruz

Topic: Consent- explicit for special categories of data

Instruments or conditions that influence this topic:

- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR)
 - Applicable National Data Protection Law (please specify)
 - Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data (Data Act)
 - Other EU or National Laws if applicable (please specify)
-

Insights provided by analysis/recommendations:

For the analysis, please specify on what grounds health data is processed and/ or shared and what differences or inconsistencies you observe in the application of the law vs. literacy EU law, across territories and/or different organizations/ players, or whether it is

Processing/ sharing shall be based on the consent (Art 9.2a, 9.4 GDPR), which shall be EXPLICIT FOR SENSITIVE DATA (SPECIAL CATEGORIES OF DATA):

- Consent cannot be implied and demands a higher degree of precision in its declaration together with a more precise definition of the purposes of processing.
 - Member States can introduce new conditions and/or limitations when it comes to the processing of genetic, biometric or health data.
 - Genomic data not defined in any regulation.
-

Gaps with potential IDERHA impact:

- Different interpretations across the EU region, which makes interjurisdictional research complex to manage.
 - Level of precision in the determination of purposes of processing is not achievable in a re-search context.
-

Possible areas for further exploration:

- How to achieve harmonization in the interpretations of consent, explicit consent and conditions applicable to genetic/ genomic information across the board for research contexts.

8.14 OTHER LEGAL BASES

IDERHA gap analysis policy brief

Name of contributor having filled out the template: Dominik Geller & Maria Bardaji-Cruz

Topic: Other legal basis

Instruments or conditions that influence this topic:

- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR)
 - Applicable National Data Protection Law (please specify)
 - Proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Euro-pean Health Data Space (EHDS)
 - Applicable National Electronic Health Record Law (please specify)
 - Other EU or National Laws if applicable (please specify)
-

Insights provided by analysis/recommendations:

For the analysis, please specify on what grounds health data is processed and/ or shared and what differences or inconsistencies you observe in the application of the law vs. literacy EU law, across territories and/or different organizations/ players, or whether it is

- According to art. 9 GDPR, the processing of sensitive data can be based on legal basis different from consent, e.g. 9.2.d, legitimate interest, 9.2.h, provision of health or social care or treatment or the management of health or social care systems and service on the basis of Union or Member State law, 9.2.i. public interest in the area of public health or (9.2.j, public interest, scientific or historical research. There are considerable dif-ferences between Member States in the application of these.
- There are also differences in the requirements for- profit and non- for-profit organiza-tions, e.g. private practice vs public institution.

Some countries have created additional requirements in the context of processing of special categories of data, like approval of the relevant Data Protection Authority, e.g. France for the cases of genetic data

Gaps with potential IDERHA impact:

- National Laws introducing additional conditions, including limitations hamper inter-jurisdictional research.

In-between scenarios, like public- private collaborations are not defined, which causes uncer-tainty in the availability of certain legal basis, e.g. public interest.

Possible areas for further exploration:

Develop standards for public- private collaborations and explore harmonization opportunities across the region

8.15 HEALTH DATA QUALITY AND UTILITY FOR THE SECONDARY USE OF HEALTH DA-TA IN THE EUROPEAN UNION - IMPLICATIONS FOR IDERHA FROM THE EURO-PEAN HEALTH DATA SPACE (EHDS) REGULATION PROPOSAL

Template for Gap-analysis task 6.2 IDERHA project

Name of contributor having filled out the template: Nadja Kartschmit

Title

Health data quality and utility for the secondary use of health data in the European Union - Implications for IDERHA from the European Health Data Space (EHDS) Regulation proposal

Potential Problems/challenges/gaps with relation to data sharing in projects like IDERHA

Stakeholders working in projects regarding data access, sharing, and integration mentioned barriers with relation to data sharing in a [workshop](#) conducted by task 6.3, including lack of trust and transparency to share data, limited data quality, incompleteness of data sets, and possible bias within data sets.

What policies or conditions influence this topic, and how:

Art. 55 of the European Health Data Space Regulation proposal states, that Health Data Access Bodies (HDAB) must provide users with metadata catalogues detailing available datasets, including source, scope, characteristics, nature, and conditions for data availability, while the European Commission (EC) sets minimum information elements for data holders.

In Art. 56, it is stated that the labelling of publicly funded datasets with electronic health data inside the European Union (EU) shall be required to demonstrate their quality and suitability for secondary data use in the EU.

Art. 57 states that the EC will create an EU Datasets Catalogue and link it to the national dataset catalogues created by HDAB and other authorized participants.

Art. 58 sets forth that the EC can establish minimum specifications for cross-border datasets for secondary use of electronic health data, considering existing infrastructures, standards, guidelines, and recommendations.

Suggestions for potential further legislative and policy development to address these potential gaps

Regarding the metadata catalogue mentioned in Art. 55, the [TEHDAS deliverable 7.2 report](#) gives recommendations for metadata publication services, metadata synchronization alternatives, and search service architecture, including implications for national datasets catalogues and the EU Datasets Catalogue.

The Big Data Steering Group of the European Medicines Agency also provides a good [practice guide](#) for the use of the metadata catalogue of real-world data sources.

In their [legal landscape analysis](#), the EHDS2 pilot identified that metadata catalogues do not or only partly exist in the Member States.

Regarding Art. 56, the [QUANTUM](#) project [kicked off](#) end of February 2024 and will run until end of June 2026. Its aim is to develop and implement a health data quality label for the secondary use of health data in the EU. The labels will allow researchers to use data with an understanding of its quality and utility, ensuring that their study and discoveries are effective and beneficial to society, promoting trust and transparency regarding the sharing of health data for secondary use.

Internal recommendations for the IDERHA consortium

1. The developments of the [QUANTUM](#) project regarding data quality and utility labels should be monitored (Art. 56).
2. IDERHA should bear in mind a dataset catalogue that would be aligned with the requirements of the [EHDS Regulation proposal](#), since the EC plans to set minimum information elements for data holders (Art. 55) and to link dataset catalogues created by authorized participants and HDAB to the EU Dataset Catalogue (Art. 57). With regards to this, the recommendations in the [TEHDAS deliverable 7.2 report](#) regarding the data discovery phase should be taken into consideration.
3. The minimum specifications for cross-border datasets for secondary use mentioned in Art. 58 should be monitored.

Possible areas for further exploration:

- Regarding the sustainability of IDERHA, it should be considered whether and how to become an authorized participant or alternatively how to join a European research infrastructure that may become such an authorized participant. This would make national datasets catalogues aligned with the future EHDS a requirement.

8.16 PROTECTION OF DATA PRIVACY AND SECURITY WITHIN THE EUROPEAN HEALTH DATA SPACE (EHDS) USING SECURE PROCESSING ENVIRONMENTS (SPEs) FOR DATA ACCESS AND ANALYSIS

Template for Gap-analysis task 6.2 IDERHA project

Name of contributor having filled out the template: Nadja Kartschmit

Title

Protection of data privacy and security within the European Health Data Space (EHDS) using Secure Processing Environments (SPEs) for data access and analysis

Potential Problems/challenges/gaps with relation to data sharing in projects like IDERHA

The [Data Governance Act](#) and the [EHDS proposal](#) use the same definition of Secure Processing Environment (SPE). The [EHDS proposal](#) states that data access and analysis should only take place in a SPE. The [TEHDAS D7.2 report](#) states, that when designing specific security requirements for SPEs, it is important to use and build on existing requirement sets, e.g. ISO/IEC 27001 Information security management systems, European Cybersecurity Certification Scheme for Cloud Services (EUCCS), Building Trusted Research Environments - Principles and Best Practices ("Five safes" report) or the Data Protection Code of Conduct.

IDERHA has proposed a federated Trusted Research Environment, which is equivalent to a SPE, but with a wider defined governance framework. IDERHA aims to adhere at best to the above mentioned "Five safes" report.

It should be examined if and to what extent IDERHA should, in addition to the "Five safes" report, conform to the data privacy requirements of SPEs outlined in the [EHDS proposal](#), bearing also in mind the considerations in the [TEHDAS D7.2 report](#).

What policies or conditions influence this topic, and how:

Under Art. 50(4) of the [EHDS proposal](#), it is stated, that the implemented legislation will detail European-wide minimum standards for SPEs. Some general requirements for SPEs are given in Art. 50 of the EHDS proposal, serving as a basis and guidance for specific requirements governed under Art. 50(4).

Suggestions for potential further legislative and policy development to address these potential gaps:

Currently, SPEs are required to comply with the [General Data Protection Regulation](#) (GDPR). GDPR regulations are relatively flexible because they rely mostly on a risk-based approach. This also implies that the level of security may vary according to the level of risk that the data controllers are ready to tolerate. Art. 51 of the [EHDS proposal](#) defines Health Data Access Bodies (HDAB) as data controllers when providing the SPE, while external SPE providers are expected to be data processors. Regarding SPE certification, it may be necessary to comply with the Cybersecurity Act (Art. 49) and [Directive \(EU\) 2022/255520 \(NIS2\)](#), Art.24., that deal with a European cybersecurity certification scheme for Information and Communication Technology (ICT) products.

In their [legal landscape analysis](#), the EDHS2 pilot found out that health data is often processed in pseudonymized format and in a SPE in the Member States.

Internal recommendations for the IDERHA consortium

1. Bearing in mind the minimum requirements for SPEs as outlined in Article 50 in the EHDS proposal, considering the considerations of the TEHDAS D7.2 report
2. Monitor the development of the specific SPE requirements under Art. 50(4) of the EHDS proposal
3. Disseminate information on the requirements and its impacts on the IDERHA architecture and sustainability to the corresponding WPs
4. Examine areas for further exploration with regards to SPE requirements

Possible areas for further exploration:

IDERHA as data holder/controller:

- When IDERHA provides the SPE in its architecture, IDERHA is data controller as defined in the [EHDS proposal](#).
- The decision whether to allow data access for external researchers might have implications for the SPE in IDERHA:

- o There is the risk of re-identifying individuals on de-identified data from multiple sources. IDERHA should ensure no permission or possibility to merge data when one researcher is involved in different parallel projects with regards to the SPE.
- o Researchers may require software or models for data analysis in the SPE and therefore it might be necessary to upload their own content to the SPE. This carries the risk of insecure software or scripts. It should be discussed whether the upload own content should be possible in the SPE. If this should be possible, measures should be taken to ensure data privacy.

8.17 EHDS INTEROPERABILITY WITH EXTERNAL INFRASTRUCTURES

Template for Gap-analysis task 6.2 IDERHA project

Name of contributor having filled out the template: Jaakko Lähteenmäki, VTT

Title

EHDS interoperability with external infrastructures

Potential Problems/challenges/gaps with relation to data sharing in projects like IDERHA

The European Health Data Space (EHDS) regulation defines the national authorities (Health Data Access Bodies, HDAB's) to be in charge of providing the permissions to access health data for secondary purposes. The HDAB's will also maintain the services needed for data discovery and set up secure processing environments (SPE's) where data can be securely processed.

When the EHDS regulation is implemented and operational projects like IDERHA would need to be interoperable with the EHDS infrastructure in order to operate fluently. The challenge is now that the EHDS regulation does not sufficiently address the needs for the EHDS infra-structure to interact with existing data sharing infrastructures and "private" data spaces.

What policies or conditions influence this topic, and how:

The main influencer is EHDS regulation and in particular the related implementing acts which will complement it in the coming years.

Suggestions for potential further legislative and policy development to address these potential gaps

Examples of topics for policy/legal development:

- definition of how existing data sharing infrastructures can connect with the EHDS data access process
 - full definition of the "authorised participant" role (currently not clear which kind of parties can be authorised participants)
 - definition of the nature of SPE's: Allow different kinds of SPE's (including private) to be setup as long as they comply with agreed common requirements (the Finnish model currently)
 - definition of SPE interoperability policy: how and under which conditions SPE's can connect with external systems, such as other SPE's (important for enabling federated processing)
 - define/improve the position of data subject to get information about data usage and to opt-out at will (opt-out defined in EHDS, but implementation details still missing)
-

Internal recommendations for the IDERHA consortium

Linking through partner's connections with projects and activities (e.g. HealthData@EU pilot project and TEHDAS2) which are currently setting up guidelines and requirements related to EHDS.

This way, we can have impact to the EHDS infrastructure and enable IDERHA to be aligned with it.

Possible areas for further exploration:

8.18 UNCLARITY OF THE ACCESS PROCEDURE FOR THE DEVELOPERS AND TOOL IN-STALLATION (WIP)

Template for Gap-analysis task 6.2 IDERHA project

Name of contributor having filled out the template: Hanna Ćwiek-Kupczyńska

Title

Unclarity of the access procedure for the developers and tool installation (WiP)

Potential Problems/challenges/gaps with relation to data sharing in projects like IDERHA

As WPI we don't expect IDERHA data providers to share any data with us directly. We are building a federated system whose components will be installed in the data providers' infra-structure and will eventually access data to perform analyses. The challenge for designing such a system is to clarify requirements and setup procedure for such a system, namely:

- Getting information about the technical capabilities of the data providers' infrastruc-ture
- Clarifying procedure and timelines for the members of the technical development team to get access to the infrastructure (to investigate the environment and assess the feasibility of our approach)
- Getting information about the formal security requirements to install the system at the data providers' infrastructure (Do we need any formal certification / external au-dit of the developed software?)

What policies or conditions influence this topic, and how:

We don't know exactly. The arrangements with data providers take a lot of time, probably due to

- the need to involve their IT departments, who are busy with other topics
- national policies or legislations, which regulate granting access to our developers to access the infrastructure
- national policies or legislations, which don't allow external software to be used to ac-cess the data (the Finnish case, where apparently the access is only possible though a certified national SPE)

Suggestions for potential further legislative and policy development to address these potential gaps

- aligning requirements and conditions for using federated solutions between institu-tions within Europe (Implementation specification for EHDS?)

Internal recommendations for the IDERHA consortium

- Clarify the conditions and timelines for the developers to be able to access the data providers' infrastructure
- Clarify the legal requirements for the system to be installed in the data providers' infrastructure (to be tested with synthetic data)
- Clarify the conditions under which the real data can be shared via the developed in-frastructure

Possible areas for further exploration:

Discussing the Finnish data providers how to interpret / extend Finnish regulations to enable them to participate in the federated infrastructure

8.19 COMMON DATA MODELS

Template for Gap-analysis task 6.2 IDERHA project

Name of contributor having filled out the template: Ravinder Claire

Title

Common Data Models

Potential Problems/challenges/gaps with relation to data sharing in projects like IDERHA

- Initial time and costs.
The upfront costs of adopting a common data model can be significant, including ex-penses related to software development, systems integration, data migration, and training programs.
- Integrating into IT systems
Integrating common data models into existing IT infrastructure often requires sub-stantial system reconfiguration and updates. This process can disrupt ongoing opera-tions and necessitates technical expertise to ensure that new and old systems work seamlessly together.
- Data migration
There is also potential for information loss during the process of mapping from the source data to the common data model and standardised vocabularies. The useful-ness of any mapped dataset largely depends on the quality and contents of the source data from which it was derived. The mapping process itself cannot overcome problems due to missing data items or observations, data fragmentation, misclassifi-cation of exposures or outcomes, or selection bias.
- Long-term support and sustainability
Ensuring that the data model remains relevant and maintainable over time requires continuous support and updates. Scalability must be considered from the outset to accommodate growing data volumes and evolving user needs.
- Interoperability
The data model must work well with other existing data standards and systems. Lack of interoperability can lead to silos of information, reducing the overall effectiveness of data integration efforts.
- Data quality
High data quality is crucial for deriving reliable insights. Common data models must include mechanisms to check and ensure the accuracy, completeness, and consisten-cy of the data they handle.
- Evolution of data
Whenever data changes, it is important to update the documentation to reflect the changes. This includes updating metadata, data dictionaries, and other documenta-tion to ensure that everyone who uses the data understands the changes.
- Training
Staff may require training to effectively use and manage the new data model. This involves understanding the nuances of the model, learning new software interfaces, and adapting to potentially altered workflows.
- Time and costs involved in running studies
Although running studies on a common data model can be streamlined, we would still need to factor in any costs and resources involved from data partners.
- Data protection officer hesitancy
In instances where data partners are running their first federated network study, there may be hesitancy of sharing results from data protection officers and could be held to a higher standard at first leading to time delays.

What policies or conditions influence this topic, and how:

"The sensitive and personal nature of healthcare data demands robust data protection and the new requirements of GDPR will need to be considered, especially in the context of com-plex real world data including digitally captured data from wearables and smart devices and the intention to develop cross member state solutions. Nevertheless, distributed data net-works where the analysis is brought to the data with no need to share patient identifiable data could provide the most likely mechanism to meet these requirements." - [A Common Data Model for Europe? - Why? Which? How? - Workshop Report](#)

Initiatives that incentivise the meaningful use of EHR systems can drive the adoption of CDMs by emphasising the need for data standardisation to enhance clinical decision-making, improve patient outcomes, and facilitate health information

exchange. A key example is IMI EHDEN, which builds upon the OMOP CDM. The EMA have also established DARWIN EU[®]. “EMA will be an authorised participant and consortium partner within the EHDS2 pilot project. EMA’s use case on thrombosis will aim to leverage DARWIN EU[®], among other platforms. DARWIN EU[®] and the EHDS2 pilot are two complementary and synergetic projects for the secondary use of health data. It will be important to evaluate how the data from the different nodes will be combined, considering data available in the Common Data Model (CDM) via DARWIN EU[®] and data available in other nodes in native format. It was also clarified that the CDM is not a pre-requisite for becoming a node in the EHDS pilot. In the future, some data sources, such as some registries for example will not be converted into a CDM. The objective will be to see how the different data sources can be combined in a single study in a meaningful way.” - [DARWIN EU[®]](#)

Please note, the following results have been taken from Deliverable 6.2 landscape review.

- The EMA, through its “Guideline on registry-based studies”, mentioned the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) model, highlighting the significance of standardised data collection frameworks to enhance interoperability and analysis across Europe. Similarly, the US FDA focused on leveraging CDMs to streamline data integration, ensuring that health data from diverse sources can be effectively combined and analysed. These documents collectively advocated for the adoption of CDMs to facilitate more efficient review processes and cross-border cooperation in safety monitoring and post-market surveillance.

While not universally recommended, several guidelines mention the use of CDMs as a potential approach for standardizing data. No documents advocate for a specific CDM, however some included examples, such as the OMOP CDM and the Sentinel Common Data Model.

Most notably, IQWiG expresses reservations about forming a ‘common data pool’ when analysing several registries. Instead, it suggests using identically designed studies in the individual registries and then summarizing these studies meta-analytically.

Suggestions for potential further legislative and policy development to address these potential gaps

- **Standardisation of Data Sharing Agreements**
Standardised data sharing agreements that comply with GDPR could facilitate cross-border data sharing.
- **incentivisation**
Introduce incentives for data partners that adopt CDMs and are involved in studies. These could include financial incentives, recognition programs, authorship on publications.
- **Education and training**
Support education and training programs focused on data sharing ethics, legal issues, and the use of common data models. These programs could target healthcare professionals, IT staff, researchers, and data controllers. This could increase trust.

Internal recommendations for the IDERHA consortium

- The DMP is a good example of what IDERHA is already doing.
- Training programs could be developed to onboard new data partners (cross-disciplinary).
- Promote a culture of data sharing by highlighting successful use cases within IDERHA and recognizing contributions.

Possible areas for further exploration:

8.20 PROTECTION OF CONFIDENTIAL COMMERCIAL INFORMATION (CCI) & TRADE SECRETS

Template for Gap-analysis task 6.2 IDERHA project

Name of contributor having filled out the template: Jakob Wested

Title

Protection of Confidential Commercial Information (CCI) & trade secrets

Potential Problems/challenges/gaps with relation to data sharing in projects like IDERHA

The pharmaceutical industry has traditionally considered a very broad spectrum of their data as being commercially confidential information and/or trade secrets, that are crucial to keep secret for their business. After a longer fight between the pharma industry, the European Ombudsman, EMA and the EU commission, and approach with a narrow interpretation of CCI in clinical trial data has been adopted. This means that it is the assumption that data sub-mitted as part of regulatory approval are not CCI unless justification of such status is pro-vided. The EU clinical trial regulation 536/2014 art 80 - 81 introduce an obligation or the commission to establish a publicly accessible database making all clinical trial data from regulatory approvals available to the public.

In the EHDS regulation an even broader pallet of data is envisioned to be made available by data holders (see art. 33) for secondary uses. Likewise, for IDERHA, it is an open ques-tion how and to what extent data should be protected based on protection of CCI or trade-secrets.

The EHDS regulation is not very specific with information on how this is done: "Electronic health data entailing protected intellectual property and trade secrets from private enter-prises shall be made available for secondary use. Where such data is made available for secondary use, all measures necessary to preserve the confidentiality of IP rights and trade secrets shall be taken." (art. 33.4)

What policies or conditions influence this topic, and how:

TRIPS agreement under WTO art 39 obliges signatories to provide protection against unfair commercial practices. This entail firstly a right to prevent disclosure of information (art. 39.2) and a right to protection of information used for regulatory purposes (art. 39.3).

In EU, art 39.2 is addressed with Dir. 2016/943 (trade secret directive), while the require-ment of art 39.3 is addressed with the availability of regulatory data exclusivity for the data submitted as part of a marketing authorization found in dir. 2001/83.

The previous decades of discourse on the intersection of transparency and protection of CCI/trade secrets have concerned fair competition within primary uses, e.g. the possibility of generic manufacturers to enter the market-based on the data of the originator. However, with RWE the use of data is not necessarily for a competing product, but for secondary uses that may be very different from the purposes for which the data was produced in the first place.

Suggestions for potential further legislative and policy development to address these potential gaps

There seem to be a significant policy gap concerning the fair protection of CCI & trade se-crets when it comes to secondary uses of data. This concerns both the discussion of what constitute CCI/TS? What measures could be used to address it? And what are the balance of interests to be considered - trust, innovation potential, patient benefits, static vs dynamic innovation impact?

Internal recommendations for the IDERHA consortium

Mapping concerns and possible solutions, e.g. from EHDS framework or establishment of the CT-database.

Possible areas for further exploration:

8.21 EVOLVING LEGAL LANDSCAPE (MAINLY EHDS)

Template for Gap-analysis task 6.2 IDERHA project

Name of contributor having filled out the template: Rada Hussein

Title

Evolving legal landscape (mainly EHDS)

Potential Problems/challenges/gaps with relation to data sharing in projects like IDERHA

Challenge: Analysing the evolving legal framework (mainly EHDS and the AI Act) to demonstrate the compliance of IDERHA with the evolving regulatory framework.

Problem/Risk: Changes in regulations can also affect the implementation, impact, and sus-tainability of IDERHA.

What policies or conditions influence this topic, and how:

With current regulations:

- IDERHA Data Sharing Agreements (DSA) with all data providers needs to address compliance with national laws in addition to EU law.
 - Harmonization of the GDPR interpretation is also required, in addition to anonymiza-tion and pseudonymization techniques.
-

Suggestions for potential further legislative and policy development to address these potential gaps

Agreed text of EHDS:

https://www.europarl.europa.eu/meetdocs/2014_2019/plmrep/COMMITTEES/CJ43/AG/2024/04-09/1299790EN.pdf

Internal recommendations for the IDERHA consortium

Example: Actions that IDERHA can put into practice

- Creating synergy with similar projects, mainly EUCAIM, GDI, and others
 - "Formal" collaboration with TEHDAS2 to keep updated with the EHDS2 development
-

Possible areas for further exploration:

How the new EHDS regulation can influence the IDERHA data "and infrastructure" access?

To which extent the adoption of regulation will affect the IDERHA data access policies and governance?

8.22 ANONYMIZATION

Template for Gap-analysis task 6.2 IDERHA project

Name of contributor having filled out the template: Anne (Fraunhofer Legal)

Title

Anonymization

Potential Problems/challenges/gaps with relation to data-sharing in projects like IDERHA

The lack of a resilient, autonomous standard of anonymization is a major detrimental factor to a project like IDERHA. Within the Project's lifetime, risk-carrying organizations are left with a maximum approach assuming full GDPR applicability to research data until deletion, since consensus regarding anonymization from an earlier point can often not be established among the partners. Whereas a project can overcome this challenge on the inner lines by applying all GDPR standards even to would-be anonymous data, the lack of reliable, functional criteria for assuming anonymization actively hinders the onboarding of 3rd Parties to the resources of the Project. After the expiration of a Project, the search for a reliable business model to extend the lifetime of the solutions and resources offered is considerably influenced from a GDPR applicability "out of uncertainty", because assuming anonymization is simply too risky and insecure.

What policies or conditions influence this topic, and how:

First and foremost, the existing statutory language should be strengthened. Presently, the outline of a definition of anonymization is derived from Recital 26 GDPR, a substantial definition within the articles of the GDPR is nowhere to be found. Secondly, heterogeneity as to application prevails amongst the EU countries and sectors. This means that anonymization concepts well-based within the logics of the GDPR are sometimes very hard to apply amongst data providers and data receivers in practice, since the acceptance/consensus of anonymization even in cases where a risk of re-identification appears neglectable under all aspects is very hard to establish.

Suggestions for potential further legislative and policy development to address these potential gaps

- Any enhancement of EU-wide, substantial harmonization of fundamental concepts, such as anonymization, health data, legal basis etc. would presumably ease the current situation
- Such harmonization must, however, be closely considered together with measures for ensuring a harmonized application. If harmonized standards are applied diversely throughout the EU (as it is the case at present), it becomes impossible to scope out research potentials. Seeing that Privacy Law is imposing risks on Data Controllers (penalties, private liability), any incalculable risk can be understood as detrimental to data sharing. Policy initiatives should push the demand for actual (not only for-mal) harmonization.

Internal recommendations for the IDERHA consortium

- IDERHA explores the strategy of pragmatism, designing its internal data sharing framework in order to allow also Partners with a high demand for legal certainty (and a correspondingly low risk appetite) to share data presumably falling under the GDPR.
- IDERHA should set out to explore new paths for establishing cross-border sector Party consensus regarding anonymization. It should do so by creating innovative technical solutions in close correspondence with the statutory legal framework

Possible areas for further exploration:

- IDERHA should explore models for a sustainable and flexible continuation beyond the Project's lifetime. Such models should base themselves of carefully thought-through correlations of a) technical and scientific needs, and b) data minimization and anonymization

8.23 REGULATORY IMPACT OF REQUIREMENTS FOR HIGH-RISK AI SYSTEMS UNDER THE EU AI ACT

Template for Gap-analysis task 6.2 IDERHA project

Name of contributor having filled out the template: Sanziana Negreanu Arboreanu

Title

Regulatory impact of requirements for high-risk AI systems under the EU AI Act

Potential Problems/challenges/gaps with relation to data sharing in projects like IDERHA

As of the date of its entry into force, AI systems developed and/or used as part of the IDERHA consortium must be compliant with the EU AI Act. The final text of the legislation is expected to be published in the Official Journal of the EU in May/June 2024 and it will enter into force after a transition period, the length depending on the scope and risk class of the applications.

What policies or conditions influence this topic, and how:

The EU is bringing forward the first worldwide legislation of Artificial Intelligence, the EU AI Act, which will encompass every AI system in the EU.

The law follows a risk-based approach which categorizes AI systems based on specific uses and risks to citizens. In healthcare, the scope of AI high-risk applications includes medical devices. Medical device that is itself an AI system or which uses an AI system will be subject to both the Medical Devices Regulation and the AI Act.

The AI Act mandates requirements for high-risk AI applications and applications for providers: Quality & Risk Management System, Technical Documentation, conformity assessment, CE marking, post-market monitoring.

Low-risk AI applications are subject to transparency obligations.

The European Commission proposal of the AI Act (2021)

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52021PC0206>

Final text of the legislation is expected May/June 2024.

Suggestions for potential further legislative and policy development to address these potential gaps

Follow the development of subsequent guidance and applicable international standards and perform impact analysis and gap assessment.

Internal recommendations for the IDERHA consortium

Ensure monitoring and adequate dissemination of information on the requirements that the new EU AI Act will bring into force, and which may impact the systems developed and/or used in IDERHA.

Facilitate connections and exchanges on the IDERHA AI systems and debates on the impact and applicable requirements under the EU AI Act to ensure compliance of the project output.

Possible areas for further exploration:

Consider the interplay between the EU AI Act and other upcoming EU legislation, such as EHDS and explore areas of overlap.

8.24 REQUIREMENTS RELATED TO DATA AND DATA GOVERNANCE UNDER THE EU AI ACT

Template for Gap-analysis task 6.2 IDERHA project

Name of contributor having filled out the template: Sanziana Negreanu Arboreanu

Title

Requirements related to data and data governance under the EU AI Act ([Regulation \(EU\) 2024/1689](#))

Potential Problems/challenges/gaps with relation to data-sharing in projects like IDERHA

The AI Act proposal lays out explicit goals for data quality, such as that training, validation and testing data sets "shall be relevant, representative, free of errors and complete" (Art. 17(3)).

Data and Data Governance under the EU AI Act ([Regulation \(EU\) 2024/1689](#))

High-risk AI systems which make use of techniques involving the training of AI models with data shall be developed on the basis of training, validation and testing data sets that

meet the quality criteria referred to below:

- Considering the intended purpose of the high-risk AI system
- Data sets should be relevant and sufficiently representative
- Data sets should be as far as possible free of error and complete
- Special category data should only be processed where necessary e.g., to detect bias and with appropriate safeguards

AI Act

- Training, validation and testing data sets shall be subject to data governance and management practices - design choices, data collection processes, origin of data, data preparation processing operations, formulation of assumptions, assessment of the availability, quantity and suitability of the datasets, examination of biases within the data (and measures to mitigate against such bias).
- The data sets should also have the appropriate statistical properties, - regards the persons or groups of persons in relation to whom the high-risk AI system is intended to be used - > mitigation of possible biases in the data sets
 - that are likely to affect the health and safety of persons,
 - have a negative impact on fundamental rights or lead to discrimination, especially feedback loops

What policies or conditions influence this topic, and how:

The EU has published the first worldwide legislation of Artificial Intelligence, the EU AI Act, which will encompass every AI system in the EU.

The AI Act brings specific data and data governance requirements for the development and deployment of AI systems.

The EU AI Act ([Regulation \(EU\) 2024/1689](#)) published in the Official Journal of the EU on 12th of July 2024

Suggestions for potential further legislative and policy development to address these potential gaps

Follow the development of subsequent guidance and applicable international standards and perform impact analysis and gap assessment.

Internal recommendations for the IDERHA consortium

In all AI systems development activities, consider the principles and requirements around data quality and data management laid out in the EU AI Act.

Possible areas for further exploration:

Analyze the use cases of the AI systems developed under the frame of IDEHRA against the data related requirements of the EU AI Act, perform gap assessment as needed and consider the requirements during the development process early on.

8.25 DYNAMIC CONSENT

Template for Gap-analysis task 6.2 IDERHA project

Name of contributor having filled out the template: Anne (Fraunhofer Legal)

Title

Dynamic consent

Potential Problems/challenges/gaps with relation to data sharing in projects like IDERHA

Data protection under the GDPR rests, i.e., on the fundamental principles of lawfulness and accountability, meaning that a given processing should always be "thought through to the end" and based on a resilient purpose-bound legal basis (e.g. informed consent/Art. 6 (1) a; Art. 9 (2) a GDPR). Under current law, if a "static" traditional consent is withdrawn, all processing based on that consent must be put to an end for the future. Imaginably, a dynamic consent "changing" on a regular basis would bring with it the challenge of design-ing/establishing a flexible and resilient operational setting / infrastructure in order to adequately ensure that data is, at all times, (only) processed if a sufficient legal basis exists.

The technical and organizational standard required by a data processing environment is set out in Art. 25 (1) GDPR (Privacy by Design). The data processing environment must technically implement data protection principles in an effective manner in order to integrate the necessary safeguards into the processing in order to meet the requirements of the GDPR and protect the rights of data subjects. Challenges to this end:

Modelling the complexity following from dynamic consents into operational technical measures (owed to the legal necessity of ensuring that data is, at all times, only processed on a sufficient legal basis)

Identifying an operational "base line" of some stability

Complying dynamically and intertemporal with all other Controller duties within the GDPR

A dynamic consent thus expectedly gives rise to new legal and technical challenges within the technical and legal setup. Whereas it may serve the autonomy of the Data Subject as the central holder of rights, it would imaginably increase complexity and reduce foreseeability for Data Controller(s) looking to base their secondary health data research on such a processing.

What policies or conditions influence this topic, and how:

The a) voluntary character and b) right to withdraw are basic features of an informed consent within current law.

Any changes to the legal, statutory requirements of informed consents should orientate themselves closely towards clarity, uniformity, and predictability. Imaginably, the substantial introduction of a dynamic consent model within the GDPR or another legal body of autonomous EU law would only lead to more insecurity and fragmentation if every national Supervisory Authority applies its own enforcement standard and interpretation. Data Controllers within the EU need to base their processing on stable and predictable terms. There is a call for policies articulating this need - prior or, at least, parallel to the political legislative process. Afterwards, not much can be done, and Data Subjects and Controllers live with the fragmentation detrimental to both groups.

Suggestions for potential further legislative and policy development to address these potential gaps

Any enhancement of EU-wide, substantial harmonization of fundamental concepts, such as anonymization, health data, legal basis etc. would presumably ease the current situation

Such harmonization must, however, be closely considered together with measures for ensuring a harmonized application. If harmonized standards are applied diversely throughout the EU (as it is the case at present), it becomes impossible to scope out research potentials. Seeing that Privacy Law is imposing risks on Data Controllers (penalties, private liability), any incalculable risk can be understood as detrimental to data sharing. Policy initiatives should push the demand for actual (not only formal) harmonization.

Internal recommendations for the IDERHA consortium

Parties should dare to actively engage with new paradigms, e.g. as to Data Sharing Approach/Framework

Courage to Co-Develop instead of falling back on old habits

IDERHA can continue to actively push the need for interdisciplinarity and agility regarding data sharing

Possible areas for further exploration:

The possibility of a dynamic consent is surely worth looking into from a transparency point-of-view - the idea being that a Data Subject would be more inclined to consent to data sharing if a larger extent of differentiated control could be facilitated

However, we already now see a certain "exhaustion" on the side of Data Subjects who are often willing to enable research but overburdened with the legal aspects. Possibly, statutory legal bases (like an EU wide harmonized research exemption available to private and public health innovators) allowing for processing for health innovation purposes but to responsible terms would make a bigger positive difference to Data Subjects as well as health innovators.

8.26 DELAYS IN DATA SHARING

Template for Gap-analysis task 6.2 IDERHA project

Name of contributor having filled out the template: Holger Fröhlich

Title

Delays in Data Sharing

Potential Problems/challenges/gaps with relation to data sharing in projects like IDERHA

Long lasting processes until data can be shared in a legally compliant manner. This is due to the necessity to have a joint controller agreement in place as well as ethical board approvals. The preparation of the material for these complex agreements is taking a long time. Subsequently, additional time is needed for the legal contract negotiations. Altogether there is a high risk, that WP2 will not meet the deadline for its first deliverable due to not having access to data.

What policies or conditions influence this topic, and how:

Example - "national policies, legislation, culture etc., identified in various documents/papers etc."

EU legislation (GDPR) and complexity of legal negotiations

Ethical board approval

Suggestions for potential further legislative and policy development to address these potential gaps

Example: frameworks, empirical examples

- Policy makers should aim for a better balance between necessary regulation of health data usage and AI on one hand and a high level of bureaucracy slowing down research and innovation on the other hand. Policy makers should understand that Europe is globally acting in a highly competitive environment. Currently, the level of regulation is - at least from a research and innovation perspective - more a barrier than a support.
 - During the last years, the legal conditions for health data usage and AI have evolved rapidly. Policy makers should understand that such a changing regulation causes uncertainty on the side of data protection officers and other legally responsible persons within organizations. This uncertainty results in a tendency to act overconservative and risk adverse. To address this issue, policy makers should: a) aim for an as much as possible stable regulation framework, b) provide templates for joint controller agreements
-

Internal recommendations for the IDERHA consortium

Example: Actions that IDERHA can put into practice

The DMP should be finalized asap to be able to start the negotiations about the joint controller agreement!

Possible areas for further exploration:

Template for Gap-analysis task 6.2 IDERHA project

Name of contributor having filled out the template:
Jakob Feldtfos Christensen. Director, DIVERSlunity

Title

Challenges of diversity and internationalisation in data sharing in health

Potential Problems/challenges/gaps with relation to data-sharing in projects like IDERHA

DIVERSlunity works with diversity and internationalisation in research and research management. Our main focus in the comments is hence mainly on the threats that data collection and the combination of data sets internationalises poses to minority groups.

Our concerns are mainly around three themes:

Collecting and Combining Data in the Age of AI

No matter the problem this last year, the solution is always "AI". The same is true in the research community. The use of AI poses challenges to data security, as this multiplies the possibilities, speed and scale of combining data. Despite the risks, data collection and analysis increasingly happen in an AI 'black box', which very few can understand and even fewer access. The risks of decoding metadata and unintended leak data and release of identities of minority persons appear to be at a scale that very few imagined just a few years back. The AI Act and national legislation cover some of these challenges, but as the science community pushes for increased opportunities for combining data and a looser interpretation of GDPR. These legislative frames have a special responsibility to protect the most vulnerable groups in our society. Their identities and data risk being used for training AI models, analysing data and advancing science without any concern for the security of these groups. While the intentions might be good, and proper and nuanced data is much needed for the development of a more inclusive AI, the price should not be paid by minorities, as has too often been the case so far.

This is particularly true when including real-life-data, where questions on protected might not be asked. In the case of social media (e.g. in a project on health and social media use) the algorithmic suggestions shows that the platform knows more about the user than asked. E.g. Instagram has never asked me whether I'm gay, but considering the algorithm mainly suggests pictures of pug, knitting videos and pictures of fit shirtless men - it clearly has a very good idea of my sexual orientation.

Politicisation

Several protected characteristics (particularly LGBTQ+ identities) have in recent years been politically contested in many countries both within and outside Europe (just this week, one of the strictest anti-LGBTQ+ legislations globally has been approved in Ghana). At the same time, we see autocratic movements, often in the same countries. While this does not present a risk right now, it does, however, give genuine future problems if research data on minorities are forced to be decoded and then used for political persecution. IDERHA should not only consider the current political environment in the EU but foresee how data collected now could be misused in an autocratic overthrow of a democratically elected government. In that political setup the consequences for minority groups could be fatal.

International collaborations

While laws and regulations on data security (e.g. GDPR) are a challenge to international research collaborations, for minority groups, these 'challenges' are crucial. For LGBTQ+ persons, the consequences of data sharing can be imprisonment or even the death penalty in certain countries if something goes wrong for technical or political reasons, as described in the two themes above. Where minority groups are based on race, ethnicity, sexual orientation, religion, ability, etc., they are at risk of prison, death, encampment or social, cultural, financial or political exclusion in their home countries or when going abroad. These real-life consequences must be first priority when developing legislation and regulatory functions for smoother international research collaboration and data sharing. It is important to note that the populist and autocratic movements described in theme two can also be seen in countries with which Europe usually has strong research collaborations.

Considering these themes in the work done by IDERHA will improve transparency for minority groups and ensure continued trust in science in all parts of society. It is important to remember that, unlike for the research community, for minorities, it isn't about protecting data but about protecting identity and, ultimately, about protecting life.

What policies or conditions influence this topic, and how:

- International laws: GDPR, EHDS, human rights acts,
- International strategies: e.g. ERA, European guidelines for international research collaboration.
- Due to an insecure world: Dual-use regulations of research data (see below).
- National conditions for minorities
- Other: Internal rules of global research funders (Private and public)

Suggestions for potential further legislative and policy development to address these potential gaps

Example: frameworks, empirical examples

Our recommendations for the three main themes are:

Data and AI

Clear legislative improvements that protect data on personal characteristics from being analysed in public AI models even when anonymised, due to the unknown content of the AI 'black box'.

Research data protected by GDPR should not be used to train AI at the risk of revealing the identity of minority individuals and the security of minority groups or individuals.

Penalties for using AI to decode GDPR-protected identities intentionally or unintentionally when combining research data with e.g. real-life data.

Clear and severe consequences for companies and research institutions who neglect the security concerns of minority groups, preferably stripping researchers and research institutions of collecting, hosting and accessing data. Otherwise, minority groups carry the entire burden and the consequences of a conscious or unconscious negligent scientific community.

Outline penalties when AI models in research circumvent the GDPR protection. An enforcing measure should be when this is used in IP and spinouts that make money while risking the security of minority groups and building on societal inequalities by making money off them.

Politicisation:

Aligning national interpretations of international laws and regulations (e.g. GDPR which is interpreted very differently in EU countries). Regarding personal characteristics, this interpretation should be the strictest possible to protect minorities from political persecution.

Clarify the political independence of e.g. GDPR compliance and define personal characteristics protected by the European Declaration of Human Rights that form a base for the "European Values" that play an increasing role in EU guidelines for international collaboration, including for research.

International collaboration:

Strengthen data protection relating to personal characteristics when research collaborations across borders due to the increasingly insecure political environment globally.

Set our procedures for retracting data collaboration in research on a nation level if minority groups are persecuted and political interference with research data puts groups at risk.

Describe sanctions for companies and research institutions, banning them from accessing data relating to personal characteristics if data has been shared with researchers or research institutions in non-secure countries, putting minority persons at risk.

Internal recommendations for the IDERHA consortium

Example: Actions that IDERHA can put into practice

- Diversity should be considered a cross-cutting theme within the project.
- Personal security should be a core consideration in all policy recommendations.
- The project should take the increased polarisation and tension globally into account. A world with more confrontations is a world where data on citizens is valuable as warfare and conflict is increasingly digital and online. Minorities are always the first victims when that happens.

Possible areas for further exploration:

See above.

Appendix 2: Topic map

9.1	Strategic investment objective	73
9.2	Interoperability standards	74
9.3	Data quality	74
9.4	Artificial intelligence	75
9.5	Data sharing and data access	75
9.6	Data protection	76
9.7	Data infrastructures	76
9.8	Digital health tools and DTx	77
9.9	Other initiatives	77

9. Appendix 2: Topic map

The topic map has been developed through the process described in section 2.2. It is constructed as a mind map and is presented here with an overview of the main topics. Following this, each topic tree is presented, with a short explanation and an overview of the topics it encompasses. Two of the branches, Information security and cybersecurity, and Digital skills, are not further elaborated here because further work is needed to determine what relevant sub-topics should be included that directly impact on IDER-HA.

Fig 1. Topic map

9.1 STRATEGIC INVESTMENT OBJECTIVES

This branch focuses on areas across the health and care and digital health ecosystems that may favour or inhibit the acceptance and rate of adoption (including investments, reimbursements) of innovations that contribute to health systems transformation, better and more equitable health outcomes and public health. Whilst not immediately impacting on the technical implementation work of IDERHA, the European digital single market, EU and national digital health policies etc. may influence the evaluation evidence that IDERHA pilots generate, and how that evidence is presented to different decision makers.

Fig 2. Strategic investment objectives

9.2 INTEROPERABILITY STANDARDS

Since IDERHA is combining and co-interpreting data from multiple sources, it will need to map data from heterogeneous representations into a common one. EHR systems and countries are progressively pro-moting the adoption of nationally mandated standards, and these are gradually being adopted when-ever systems are upgraded. On top of this is the mandated use of the European Electronic Health Rec-ord Exchange Format by the European Health Data Space for primary data use (identifiable data). These formats will increasingly be the representation in which IDERHA receives data from its external data sources. IDERHA will also need to adopt a suitable common data model and relevant semantics for consolidating its data and acting as the master representation for machine and human learning. This should be as aligned as possible with existing observational data models. Other interoperability issues are also mentioned in this branch.

Fig 3. Interoperability standards

9.3 DATA QUALITY

It is now well recognised that data made available for reuse should be quality assessed. This has most strongly highlighted in relation to AI but also applies to data reused for decision making evidence gen-eration. In the near future the EHDS Regulation will give rise to a standard data quality label that IDER-HA data sets should have. A new EC project called QUANTUM (2024-2026) is charged with developing this label specification and promoting its uptake.

Fig 4. Data quality

9.4 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Although not strictly a data topic, the trustworthy and ethical development of AI critically relies upon the data that is used for training, as well as the quality processes that are adopted during the AI development and afterwards. This part of the tree lists a number of areas of quality and ethics, including explicitly the compliance with the European ethical principles and the proposed AI Act, that IDERHA must apply.

Fig 5. Artificial intelligence

9.5 DATA SHARING AND DATA ACCESS

IDERHA is going to be a beneficiary of data sharing by others and may have expectations on the adherence of those data providers to good practices in the provision of data and metadata. However, probably more importantly, IDERHA expects to make at least some of the data it acquires (and which can adequately anonymised) available to other external research communities as shareable data or as data that can be queried through a federated architecture. Most of the elements of this branch are not yet reflected in formal policies or legislation, but there is mature emerging good practice that can be adopted and should be adopted, such as the FAIR principles.

Fig 6. Data sharing and access

9.6 DATA PROTECTION

Compliance with data protection legislation, in particular the GDPR, is a non-negotiable obligation on IDERHA and all of its partners. However, there are areas that are not precisely specified and not interpreted uniformly across member states, such as the adequacy of safeguards for the use of pseudonymised data. There are also complimentary areas of legislation, such as the Data Governance Act, that offer opportunities for IDERHA to consider for some of its processing activities. The EHDS Regulation draft and its stipulations to Health Data Access Bodies within Member States will also be important to monitor in collaboration with Task 6.5.

Fig 7. Data protection

9.7 DATA INFRASTRUCTURES

Data infrastructures is a broad topic, and to some extent IDERHA is creating one itself as the IDERHA platform. In such technical framework, the IDERHA platform will act as a data source that plugs into national and European infrastructures. Whilst not directly impacting the internal workings of most work packages, it will be essential for IDERHA to monitor the regulatory and policy landscape, in particular the EHDS Regulation draft and its connections with MyHealth@EU and HealthData@EU.

Fig 8. Data infrastructures

9.8 DIGITAL HEALTH TOOLS AND DTx

Through its cases studies involving lung cancer, IDERHA will be creating AI solutions that will be embedded within digital health tools, to be used by patients in a piloting mode. Other digital innovations may also be developed during the project time. The sustainability strategy for these tools is still being elucidated, but if any of these have the potential to be scaled up and marketed post project, then they will need to be certified and approved at some point. Even if these assessments will take place after the project ends, many of them include formative evaluation components which means that good practices and documentation may need to be commenced during the project, at the time of development.

Fig 9. Digital health tools and DTx

9.9 OTHER INITIATIVES

IDERHA is conducting its innovations at a time when there are other parallel initiatives that are tackling some aspects of large-scale data Reeves, and it will be of value to the project and have greater societal impact if we can establish good collaborative touch points with those projects, support each other with challenges and reinforce each other’s good practices, and lobby for change collectively. These are not examples of policy instruments or policy gaps, but channels through which we may amplify our impact.

Fig 10. Other initiatives

